

Contribution to the knowledge of the bee fauna (Hymenoptera, Apoidea, Anthophila) in Serbia

Sonja Mudri-Stojnić¹, Andrijana Andrić², Zlata Markov-Ristić¹,
Aleksandar Đukić³, Ante Vujić¹

1 University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Biology and Ecology, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 2, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia **2** University of Novi Sad, BioSense Institute, Dr Zorana Đinđića 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia **3** Scientific Research Society of Biology and Ecology Students “Josif Pančić”, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 2, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

Corresponding author: Sonja Mudri-Stojnić (sonja.mudri-stojnic@dbe.uns.ac.rs)

Academic editor: Thorleif Dörfel | Received 13 April 2021 | Accepted 1 June 2021 | Published 2 August 2021

<http://zoobank.org/88717A86-19ED-4E8A-8F1E-9BF0EE60959B>

Citation: Mudri-Stojnić S, Andrić A, Markov-Ristić Z, Đukić A, Vujić A (2021) Contribution to the knowledge of the bee fauna (Hymenoptera, Apoidea, Anthophila) in Serbia. ZooKeys 1053: 43–105. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1053.67288>

Abstract

The current work represents summarised data on the bee fauna in Serbia from previous publications, collections, and field data in the period from 1890 to 2020. A total of 706 species from all six of the globally widespread bee families is recorded; of the total number of recorded species, 314 have been confirmed by determination, while 392 species are from published data. Fourteen species, collected in the last three years, are the first published records of these taxa from Serbia: *Andrena barbareae* (Panzer, 1805), *A. clarkella* (Kirby, 1802), *A. fulvicornis* (Schenck, 1853), *A. intermedia* (Thomson, 1870), *A. lapponica* (Zetterstedt, 1838), *A. pandellei* (Pérez, 1895), *A. paucisquama* (Noskiewicz, 1924), *A. simillima* (Smith, 1851), *Panurginus herzi* (Morawitz, 1892), *Epeoloides coecutiens* (Fabricius, 1775), *Nomada leucophthalma* (Kirby, 1802), *Chelostoma nasutum* (Pérez, 1895), *Hoplitis claviventris* (Thomson, 1872), and *Dasygaster pyrotrichia* (Förster, 1855). Almost all the species recorded so far in Serbia belong to the West-Palaeartic biogeographical region, except *Megachile sculpturalis* (Smith, 1853), which is an alien invasive species native to East Asia. According to the European Red List of bees, 221 species listed in this paper were assessed as Data Deficient; threatened species mostly belong to the families Apidae with 13 species, Colletidae with eight species, and Halictidae with five species. This study contributes to the knowledge of the distribution of bee species in Europe. The present work provides a baseline for future research of wild bee diversity in Serbia and neighbouring regions at the local and regional levels, and a basis for their conservation.

Keywords

diversity, fauna, Serbia, wild bees

Introduction

The first available data on the faunistic research of Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Anthophila in the Balkan countries derives from the late 19th century, from the period of the Austro-Hungarian Empire. At that time, scientists were collecting data on the wild bee fauna while travelling through the area of today's Balkan countries, or they researched parts of the countries where they lived. The borders and names of the Balkan countries have changed several times since then. Therefore, in the present paper, the localities are shown within the current borders of the Republic of Serbia.

The earliest publication, which provided the data on the bee fauna of Serbia is by Korlević (1890), who recorded 15 bee species in the Pannonian Region of the country. Six years later, Apfelbeck (1896) collected specimens of 101 wild bee species in southeast Serbia during his travels through Balkan countries. Soon after that, Mocsáry (1897) published "Fauna Regni Hungarie". This publication contains significant data from Deliblato Sands in today's Serbia, where 199 wild bee species were recorded. Vorgin (1918) provided data on the bee fauna from Fruška Gora Mountain and several sites on the margins of the Danube, where 97 bee species were recorded, and for the first time from all families of Apoidea. The most reliable and comprehensive publication on the bee fauna of Serbia was published by Lebedev (1931). Bee specimens were collected across several Balkan countries by more than ten experts and encompassed 258 bee species from former Yugoslavia, among which 203 were from Serbia. Most of these bees belong to Central European species and the whole fauna was very similar to that of Hungary and Romania (Lebedev 1931). Vorgin (1955) published contributions to the fauna Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Anthophila of Yugoslavia, including new data on bee fauna and sites for 114 bee species, which were recorded in Serbia. Rafajlović and Seleši (1958) presented data from Alfred Taubert's collection, who collected insects for 35 years (1909–1944) in the territory of former Yugoslavia. In Serbia, 267 bee species were recorded mostly in the Vojvodina province, in the vicinity of the city of Subotica and Deliblato Sands. The value of the collection lies in the fact that Taubert collected twice as many species as Mocsáry (1897) in the same area (Rafajlović and Seleši 1958).

After World War II, many authors mainly focused their research on studying the ecology or life history and biology of some species, or the bee diversity of certain regions. Grozdanić studied the life history and ecology of *Lasioglossum marginatum* (Brullé, 1832) (as *Halictus marginatus* Brullé, 1832), *L. interruptum* (Panzer, 1798) (as *H. interruptus* (Panzer, 1798)), *L. malachurum* (Kirby, 1802) (as *H. malachurus* (Kirby, 1802)), *H. sajoi* (Blüthgen, 1923), *H. maculatus* (Smith, 1848), *H. asperulus* (Pérez, 1895), *Seladonia kessleri* (Bramson, 1879) (as *H. kessleri* Bramson, 1879), *Osmia bicornis* Linnaeus, 1758, *O. bicolor* (Schrank, 1781), *O. rufohirta* (Latreille, 1811), *O. bidentata* (Morawitz, 1876), *Xylocopa violacea* (Linnaeus, 1758), *X. valga* (Gerstäcker, 1872), *X. iris* Christ, 1791 (as *X. cyanescens* Brullé, 1832), *Bombus pascuorum* Scopoli, 1763 (as *B. agrorum* (Fabricius, 1787)), *Apis mellifera* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Anthophora plumipes* Pallas, 1772 (as *A. acervorum* (Linnaeus, 1758)), *A. plagiata* Illiger, 1806 (as *A. parietina* (Fabricius, 1793)), *A. salviae* (Panzer, 1804) (as

A. crinipes Smith, 1854), *A. pubescens* (Fabricius, 1781), *Eucera* (*Tetralonia*) *lyncea* (as *Tetralonia lyncea* (Mocsáry, 1879)), *Eucera* (*Tetralonia*) *nana* (as *T. nana* (Morawitz, 1874)), *Systropha planidens* (Giraud, 1861), *S. curvicornis* (Scopoli, 1770), *Eucera excisa* (Mocsáry, 1879), *Megachile ericetorum* (Lepeletier, 1841), and *Ceratina* spp. (Grozđanić 1926, 1928, 1930, 1950a, b, 1956, 1958a, b, 1960, 1961, 1965, 1966, 1968, 1969a–c, 1970, 1971a, b, 1972a, b, 1974; Grozđanić and Čolović 1955a, b; Grozđanić and Stevanović 1959, 1965; Grozđanić and Krunić 1961; Grozđanić and Vasić 1965a, b, 1966a, b, 1967a, b, 1968, 1970; Grozđanić and Mučalica 1966, 1968a, b, 1969, 1973; Grozđanić and Baranov 1963; Grozđanić and Radivojević 1972). Grozđanić and Vasić (1965c, 1966a) published two papers on their entomological research in the vicinity of Belgrade and their faunistic lists contained 35 bee species. Živojinović (1950) provided a comprehensive monograph on the fauna of insects from eastern Serbia and recorded 112 bee species in the Majdanpek region, on the southern Carpathian Mountain. Petrik (1958) published the results of a two-year study of the insect fauna in the area of Deliblato Sands, where he recorded 58 bee species. Vasić studied the life history and biology of *Lasioglossum marginatum* (as *Halictus marginatus*), *H. quadricinctus* (Fabricius, 1776), *H. scabiosae* (Rossi, 1790), *Megachile albisecta* Klug, 1817 (as *Megachile sericans* Fonscolombe, 1832) (Vasić 1966, 1967, 1968, 1970, 1979a, b). Mučalica, Z. studied the biology and life history of *Halictus fulvipes* (Klug, 1817), *Anthophora plagiata* (as *A. parietina*), and *A. salviae* (as *A. crinipes*) (Mučalica 1968, 1984, 1987a, b, 1990, 1997). Mučalica and Stanivljević (2005) studied the nesting biology of *Megachile willughbiella* (Kirby, 1802). Grozđanić and Mučalica researched the fauna of Hymenoptera across former Yugoslavia; Mučalica collected insects for 33 years (1965–1997) in the area of Serbia and Grozđanić collected insects in the period from 1963 to 1972. Both collections are preserved in the Natural History Museum in Belgrade. The present paper lists 181 bee species recorded in Serbia by the above authors. Krunić studied two important wild bee pollinators of Serbian orchards, namely *Osmia cornuta* (Latreille, 1805) and *O. bicornis* (as *O. rufa* (Linnaeus, 1758)) in all aspects of their life history such as diapause, overwintering, distribution, population management, etc. (Krunić et al. 1989, 1991, 1992a, 1995a, 1996, 1997, 1998, 1999, 2001, 2005; Krunić and Stanisavljević 2006a–d). The other pollinator bee species he studied was *Megachile rotundata* (Fabricius, 1793) (Krunić et al. 1985, 1992b, c, 1995b, 1997). Krunić, Radović and Brajković (1988) published a list of the Megachilide family collected in former Yugoslavia. Krunić also studied the population of honey bees, mostly in the Pannonian region (Krunić 1967, 1986, 1994; Krunić et al. 1994). Stanisavljević continued research into bee pollinators in orchards, mostly *Osmia cornuta* and *O. bicornis* (as *O. rufa*), from the environmental, conservation, morphology, and management aspects (Stanisavljević 1996, 2000, 2009; Stanisavljević et al. 1997a, b, 1999, 2000a, b, 2013). Stanisavljević and Nedić (2008) published a paper on the role of bees in orchard pollination in Serbia. Stanisavljević (2013) published a list of bee species from the Megachilidae family of Fruška Gora. Stanisavljević and Tomović (2006) presented the results of alfalfa seed production with the use of *Megachile rotundata*

in Serbian agricultural farms. Mudri-Stojnić studied bee fauna in agro-ecosystems of Vojvodina province from 2011. Markov studied bee fauna in protected areas of Vojvodina province (Markov et al. 2016) and their economic aspect (Markov 2017). Đukić studied the bee fauna of the Vlasina region in southeast Serbia; in two years (2019–2020), he recorded 99 bee species.

The importance of bees in terrestrial ecosystems, as well as their ecosystem role in the process of pollination of agricultural crops and wild plants, is widely known. In many European countries, Red Data Books or Red Lists of bees have been produced at the national level. Some European countries have developed specific national actions in order to enhance bee populations and to arrest decline, introduced legislation with the aim of legally protecting all or some species of bees, and/or produced checklists of bees. For some Balkan countries, such as Serbia, data on the diversity of bees are scarce. Among the reasons for such a situation are an insufficient number of wild bee experts and the absence of proper collections. Up-to-date entomological research programmes of wild bees have not been spatially systematic, so certain areas of Serbia have been studied more, while others less. Although there is clear evidence of a decline in pollinators diversity and abundance across Europe (Potts et al. 2010; Nieto et al. 2014; Goulson et al. 2015), there are no initiatives or activities to protect wild bee species or their habitats in Serbia.

The present study summarises for the first time all the available records of species of wild bees in Serbia. This paper is not intended as a national checklist of bees, since there are undoubtedly more species yet to be found. The aims of this study are: 1) to review the records on the bee fauna, according to bibliographic sources known to the authors, 2) to present some more recent observations, and finally 3) to provide an updated preliminary list of the species of bees occurring in Serbia. The major purpose of this article is to broaden the knowledge of bee diversity in Serbia and pave the way for future research of wild bee fauna at local and regional levels. Another important aim is to improve an understanding of the status and trends of European pollinators.

Materials and methods

Study area

Serbia is situated in central and southeast Europe, mostly in the central Balkan peninsula, while its northern part spreads over the southern belt of the Pannonian Plain. The country's total area is 88,361 km² (Spatial Plan RS 2021–2035, Official Gazette of RS No. 48/19). The main geographic units in Serbia are the Pannonian Region in the north, which covers a third of the country, the Peripannonian Region in the central part of the country, which chiefly consists of hills traversed by rivers, and the mountain and basin region which are dominant in the south. The Carpathian Mountains and the Balkan Mountains stretch in the north-south direction through east Serbia. The Dinaric Arc stretches in the west and southwest. The climate of Serbia is under the

influences of the landmass of Eurasia, the Atlantic Ocean, and the Mediterranean Sea. It classifies as a warm-humid continental or humid subtropical climate. In the north of the country, the climate is more continental, whereas south and southeast Serbia are influenced by the Mediterranean climate (Stevanović and Stevanović 1995). In the north of Serbia, the Pannonian Plain is a lowland landscape with large rivers (e.g. the Danube, Sava, and Tisa) while to the south hilly or mountainous landscapes are intersected by river valleys. In Vojvodina, there is a large sandy area called Deliblato Sands, which is rare and unusual in inland Europe. The main habitat types are: steppe grasslands and wooded steppe, mesophilic meadows, saline grassland, shrubs, wetland, mainly deciduous southern European forests, coniferous forests, and high-mountain rocky areas and pastures.

Serbia is a country with a number of rich ecosystems, and species diversity of many groups of organisms is high and contributes to a significant part of Europe's biodiversity. According to previous research, in the territory of the Republic of Serbia there are: 39% of the European vascular flora, 74% of the European bird fauna, 67% of the European mammal fauna, 51% of the European fish fauna, and 49% of the European reptile and amphibian fauna (IUCN 2021). Conserved habitats, from lowland grasslands and wetlands, through forests and other higher habitats, to high mountain areas intersected with gorges and major lowland rivers (e.g. the Danube, Sava, and Tisa), all form the basis for its biodiversity. There are 462 protected areas in Serbia on 7.65% of its surface, among which are five National Parks, 18 Nature Parks, 20 Protected Landscapes, 68 Nature Reserves, six Protected Habitats, and 308 Natural Monuments (Spatial Plan RS 2021–2035, Official Gazette of RS No. 48/19). The ecological network that consists of ecologically significant areas and ecological corridors covers 101 nationally and internationally significant areas, comprising 21% of the total area of Serbia. Most areas within the ecological network have an international status based on several aspects: 61 Emerald Areas of Special Conservation Importance – ASCI; 42 Important Bird Areas – IBA; 61 Important Plant Areas – IPA; 40 Prime Butterfly Areas – PBA; ten Ramsar sites. The ecological network also includes other spaces and places that have yet to be spatially identified (Spatial Plan RS 2021–2035, Official Gazette of RS No. 48/19). Agricultural production on annual crops is mostly present in the Pannonian Plain. Serbia produces various agricultural products, mostly grains, fruits, and vegetables. According to the FAOSTAT, Serbia is among the top five world producers of raspberries and plums, which are mainly produced in the southwest. Agricultural landscapes occupy 63.7% of the territory (Spatial Plan RS 2021–2035, Official Gazette of RS No. 48/19).

Methodology

This paper represents a list of bee species in Serbia based on the compiled data known to the authors, gathered from available entomological collections and literature sources between 1890 and 2020, and our own faunistic studies in the decade 2010–2020. Therefore, it includes previously published and unpublished data, supplied by different

specialists, as well as some recent records from the authors of this paper. In total, more than 100 publications were examined for relevant records. Additionally, the present list was based on reviewing a database from the online Checklist of Western Palaearctic Bees (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Anthophila) by Kuhlmann et al. (2020), which provides basic information on bee diversity in the Serbian region.

The following abbreviations are used in the text:

- AD coll.** Aleksandar Đukić private collection (determined by Zsolt Józán, specialist in Aculeata research in Central Europe; bee specialist Dr Andrej Gogala from the Slovenian Museum of Natural History, Ljubljana, Slovenia; Prof. Denis Michez, Laboratory of Zoology, University of Mons, and PhD student Jelle Devalez, Department of Geography, University of the Aegean);
- AZ coll.** Aleksandra Zatezalo collection of the Institute for Nature Conservation of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia (determined by Zsolt Józán);
- FSUNS** Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia;
- SG coll.** Simeun Grozdanić collection of the NHMB (Natural History Museum, Belgrade), Serbia;
- ZM coll.** Zoran Mučalica collection of the NHMB, Serbia.

The cited PhD thesis of Stanisavljević (2000) is based on the material collected by the author, data from the available private collections and collections of the NHMB, as well as data from the published literature, which refer to the researched area. PhD theses of Markov (2017) and Mudri-Stojnić (2018) are based on the material from the collection of the FSUNS. The material from the FSUNS entomological collection were determined by Zsolt Józán. The cited Živojinović (1950) and Petrik (1958) collections are not preserved. The paper by Vorgin (1955) was based on data from the collection of the Croatian Natural History Museum, whose data had been collected for ca. 50 years. The data on registered species from the genera *Andrena* (Fabricius, 1775) and *Bombus* (Latreille, 1802) were not published in the paper by Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); the authors had no knowledge of that collection, which at the time was kept in the Zoological Museum of Zagreb; these data were published by Vorgin (1955). The Alfréd Taubert collection was identified by Alfréd Taubert himself with the help of Paul Blüthgen; unfortunately, professional curation of the collection was not provided, and as a consequence, the collection has not been preserved. Lebedev (1931) compiled data from the collection of the Entomological Institute of Belgrade. The collection contained specimens mostly collected by J. Vagnera and A. Matisena from all over Serbia. The species from the material were determined by Lebedev, P. Blüthgen (*Halictus* sensu lato species), and V. Popov (*Bombus* species). This collection was destroyed during World War II. The publication by Vorgin (1918) contains data from the A. Hensch collection and new data collected by Vorgin, as well as bee collections from the Croatian Natural History Museum. The species from the Apfelbeck, V. (1896) material were determined by H. Friese. The species from the Korlević (1890) material were determined by: A. Mocsary, A. Braunis, F. Koh, H. Friese, F.W. Konow,

Figure 1. Map of Serbia showing the locations where specimens were collected.

L. Biró, and G. Mayr. The Anton Korlević entomological collection is housed in the Croatian Natural History Museum.

A map of Serbia (Fig. 1) shows the 193 sites where sampling was carried out. The localities were gathered from publications cited in this paper and from data labels in the collections from the Natural History Museum, Belgrade, from the Institute for Nature Conservation of Serbia, and the AÐ collection.

List format

Nieto et al. (2014) were consulted for the nomenclature of the accepted species names, and the nomenclatural and classification changes suggested by Rasmont et al. (2017) and Dorchin et al. (2018) were adopted. Kuhlmann et al. (2020) and Michez et al. (2019) were consulted for classification and the authorities. For clarification of synonyms and other names mentioned in various cited publications, mostly Kuhlmann et al. (2020), but also other sources, were consulted (NBN 2020; Rasmont and Haubruge 2020; Zicha 2020). The valid species' names are shown in bold; families, genera, and species are arranged in alphabetical order. For each species, all references providing records are listed by year; if different from the valid name, the name by which the species is referred to in the original publication is written after "as". Species with no records in Serbia after the 19th century are marked with an asterisk (*). Among the species confirmed by determination of studied material, examined specimens are marked with the double oblique hyphen (≍) and non-marked species represent records based only on literature data. The black small squares (▪) mark species for which the only source of occurrence in Serbia is the Checklist of the Western Palearctic Bees (Kuhlmann et al. 2020). At the end of each species paragraph, the IUCN Red List Category (Europe), according to Nieto et al. (2014), is given in square brackets (abbreviations: CR – Critically Endangered, EN – Endangered, VU – Vulnerable, NT – Near Threatened, LC – Least Concern, DD – Data Deficient). Data about the new material examined are given for the specimens that represent the first published records of species for Serbia.

Results

The list of bees in Serbia presented consists of six families, 58 genera, and 706 species, recorded during the past 130 years. Of the total number of the recorded species, 314 have been confirmed by determination, while 392 species are from literature data. The reported families with the numbers of species (confirmed by determination/based only on literature data) are: Apidae 226 species (91/135), Megachilidae 148 species (62/86), Halictidae 138 species (73/65), Andrenidae 112 species (68/44), Colletidae 69 species (14/55), and Mellitidae 13 species (6/7). The present list includes 14 species with no previously published records for Serbia: *Andrena barbareae* (Panzer, 1805), *A. clarkella* (Kirby, 1802), *A. fulvicornis* (Schenck, 1853), *A. intermedia* (Thomson, 1870), *A. lapponica* (Zetterstedt, 1838), *A. pandellei* (Pérez, 1895), *A. paucisquama* (Noskiewicz, 1924), *A. simillima* (Smith, 1851), *Panurginus herzi* (Morawitz, 1892), *Epeoloides coecutiens* (Fabricius, 1775), *Nomada leucophthalma* (Kirby, 1802), *Chelostoma nasutum* (Pérez, 1895), *Hoplitis claviventris* (Thomson, 1872), and *Dasypoda pyrotrichia* (Förster, 1855).

The diversity and proportional representation of bee families are given in Table 1, and the summary of numbers and proportions of bee species within each category of threat according to the European Red List are presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Diversity and proportional representation of bee families in Serbia, Europe, and the West Palearctic region (WP).

Family	Serbia				Europe (Nieto et al. 2014 + Rasmont et al. 2017)		WP* (Rasmont et al. 2017)	
	No of genera	% of 58 genera	No of species	% of 706 species	No of species	% of 1,965+86 species	No of species	% of 3,408 species
Andrenidae	6	10.3	112	15.9	465+24	23.8	716	21.0
Apidae	18	31.0	226	32.0	561+16	28.1	926	27.2
Colletidae	2	3.4	69	9.8	146	7.1	270	7.9
Halictidae	12	20.7	138	19.5	314+30	16.8	585	17.2
Megachilidae	17	29.3	148	21.0	442+14	22.2	852	25.0
Mellitidae	3	5.2	13	1.8	37+2	1.9	59	1.7

*area between 26° and 72° latitude north and from 32° longitude west to 62° longitude east.

Table 2. Summary of numbers and proportion of bee species within each category of threat.

The European Red List	Europe (Nieto et al. 2014)		Serbia	
Category	No of species	% of 1,942 species*	No of species	% of 704 species**
Critically Endangered	7	0.4	1	0.1
Endangered	46	2.4	18	2.6
Vulnerable	24	1.2	10	1.4
Near Threatened	101	5.2	64	9.1
Least Concern	663	34.1	390	55.4
Data Deficient	1,101	56.7	221	31.4

*does not include the Not Applicable species in Europe, e.g., species of marginal occurrence (Nieto et al. 2014).

**does not include two species not listed in the European Red List.

Andrenidae (6 genera; 112 species)

Andrena Fabricius, 1775 (104 species)

1. **■***Andrena aberrans* Eversmann, 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
2. **♂***Andrena aeneiventris* Morawitz, 1872 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Vorgin (1955); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
3. ******Andrena albopunctata* (Rossi, 1792) in Mocsáry (1897); as *Andrena funebris* (Panzer, 1798) in Korlević (1890). [LC]
4. **♂***Andrena alfkenella* Perkins, 1914 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
5. *Andrena argentata* Smith, 1844 in Vorgin (1955); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
6. *Andrena atrata* Friese, 1887 in Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); as *Andrena bicarinata* (Morawitz, 1876) in Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
7. **♂***Andrena barbareae* Panzer, 1805 **New material examined:** 1 ♀; Vlasina, Veliki Čemernik; 42.7368°N, 22.2723°E; 25 May 2019; M. Vujić leg.; Andrej Gogala det.; AĐ coll. 1 ♀; Vlasina, Vrtop; 42.7904°N, 22.372°E; 20 Jul. 2019; A. Đukić leg.; Andrej Gogala det.; AĐ coll. [DD]
8. *Andrena barbilabris* (Kirby, 1802) as *Andrena sericea* Smith, 1791 in Vorgin (1955); as *Andrena albicrus* (Kirby, 1802) in Mocsáry (1897). [DD]

9. *Andrena bicolor* Fabricius, 1775 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Andrena gwynana* (Kirby, 1802) in Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); AĐ coll [LC]
10. *Andrena bimaculata* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
11. *Andrena brumanensis* Friese, 1899 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Andrena clypeata* Brullé, 1832 in Živojinović (1950). [LC]
12. *Andrena bucephala* Stephens, 1846 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
13. *Andrena carantonica* Pérez, 1902 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); ZM coll.; as *Andrena jacobi* Perkins, 1921 in Lebedev (1931). [DD]
14. *Andrena chrysopyga* Schenck, 1853 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Vorgin (1955, 1918); Lebedev (1931); ZM coll. [DD]
15. *Andrena cineraria* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
16. *Andrena clarkella* (Kirby, 1802) **New material examined:** 1 ♀; Vlasina Rid; 42.7253°N, 22.3284°E; 21 Jul. 2019; A. Đukić leg.; Andrej Gogala det.; AĐ coll. [DD]
17. *Andrena coitana* (Kirby, 1802) as *Andrena shawella* (Kirby, 1802) in Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
18. *Andrena colletiformis* Morawitz, 1874 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Apfelbeck (1896). [DD]
19. *Andrena combaella* Warncke, 1966 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018). [DD]
20. *Andrena combinata* (Christ, 1791) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); ZM coll. [DD]
21. *Andrena comta* Eversmann, 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [EN]
22. *Andrena confinis* Stöckhert, 1930 in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Živojinović (1950).
23. *Andrena congruens* Schmiedeknecht, 1884 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); AĐ coll. [LC]
24. *Andrena cordialis* Morawitz, 1877 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016). [DD]
25. *Andrena curvana* Warncke, 1965 in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016). [DD]
26. *Andrena decipiens* Schenck, 1861 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
27. *Andrena denticulata* (Kirby, 1802) in Lebedev (1931). [DD]
28. *Andrena dorsalis* Brullé, 1832 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); ZM coll. [DD]
29. *Andrena dorsata* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); as *Andrena dubitata* Schenck, 1870 in Vorgin (1955); Apfelbeck (1896). [DD]
30. *Andrena erythrocnemis* Morawitz, 1870 in Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
31. *Andrena fimbriata* Brullé, 1832 in Mocsáry (1897). [DD]

32. *Andrena flavipes* Panzer, 1799 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Grozdanić (1971b); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); AZ coll.; ZM coll.; also as *Andrena extricata* Smith, 1849 in Apfelbeck (1896); as *Andrena extricata* in Mocsáry (1897); Korlević (1890); as *Andrena fulvicrus* Dufour, 1841 in Petrik (1958). [LC]
33. *Andrena florea* Fabricius, 1793 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Apfelbeck (1896); as *Andrena rosae* var. *austriaca* Schmied. in Živojinović (1950); as *Andrena austriaca* Panzer, 1798 in Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
34. *Andrena fulvago* (Christ, 1791) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
35. *Andrena fulvicornis* Schenck, 1853 **New material examined:** 1 ♀; Beočin, Fruška gora, Časorske livade; 45.1894°N, 19.7451°E; 15 Jun. 2018; S. Mudri-Stojnić leg.; Zsolt Józán det.; FSUNS. [DD]
36. *Andrena fuscosa* Erichson, 1835 as *Andrena ephippium* Spinola, 1838 in Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
37. *Andrena gelriae* van der Vecht, 1927 in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); AZ coll. [DD]
38. *Andrena gravida* Imhoff, 1832 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931); AÐ coll.; AZ coll.; ZM coll. [DD]
39. *Andrena grozdanici* Osytshnjuk, 1975 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mučalica (1984). [DD]
40. *Andrena haemorrhoea* (Fabricius, 1781) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); AÐ coll.; AZ coll.; as *Andrena albicans* auct. nec Müller in Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
41. *Andrena hattorfiana* (Fabricius, 1775) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Lebedev (1931); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); AÐ coll. [NT]
42. *Andrena bedikae* Jaeger, 1934 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Vorgin (1955). [DD]
43. *Andrena humilis* Imhoff, 1832 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931); in Apfelbeck (1896); AÐ coll.; as *Andrena fulvescens* Smith, 1847 in Vorgin (1955, 1918). [DD]
44. *Andrena hungarica* Friese, 1887 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
45. *Andrena hypopolia* Schmiedeknecht, 1884 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Vorgin (1955, 1918); Mocsáry (1897); Korlević (1890). [DD]
46. *Andrena impunctata* Pérez, 1895 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016). [LC]
47. *Andrena intermedia* Thomson, 1870 **New material examined:** 1 ♀; Vlasina, Veliki Čemernik; 42.7368°N, 22.2723°E; 21 Jul. 2019; M. Vujić leg.; Andrej Gogala det.; AÐ coll. [LC]

48. *Andrena labialis* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Grozdanić (1970); Vorgin (1955, 1918); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); AZ coll.; ZM coll. [DD]
49. *Andrena labiata* Fabricius, 1781 in Lebedev (1931); ZM coll. [DD]
50. *Andrena lagopus* Latreille, 1809 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
51. *Andrena lapponica* Zetterstedt, 1838 **New material examined:** 1 ♀; Vlasina, Gadžini; 42.7378°N, 22.3042°E; 25 May 2019; A. Đukić leg.; Andrej Gogala det.; AÐ coll. [LC]
52. *Andrena latbyri* Alfken, 1899 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Grozdanić (1970); ZM coll. [DD]
53. *Andrena limata* Smith, 1853 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); as *Andrena pectoralis* Schmiedeknecht, 1883 in Vorgin (1955); Mocsáry (1897); Korlević (1890). [DD]
54. *Andrena limbata* Eversmann, 1852 in Lebedev (1931). [DD]
55. *Andrena marginata* Fabricius, 1776 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
56. *Andrena mehelyi* Alfken, 1936 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
57. *Andrena minutula* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Lebedev (1931); AÐ coll.; as *Andrena parvula* (Kirby, 1802) in Apfelbeck (1896). [DD]
58. *Andrena minutuloides* Perkins, 1914 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
59. *Andrena mocsaryi* Schmiedeknecht, 1884 in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016). [LC]
60. *Andrena morio* Brullé, 1832 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Petrik (1958); Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [DD]
61. *Andrena nasuta* Giraud, 1863 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
62. *Andrena nigroaenea* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Vorgin (1955). [LC]
63. *Andrena nitida* (Müller, 1776) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Vorgin (1955); Mocsáry (1897); AÐ coll. [LC]
64. *Andrena nitidiuscula* Schenck, 1853 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Mocsáry (1897); as *Andrena lucens* Imhoff, 1868 in Vorgin (1955, 1918); Korlević (1890). [LC]
65. *Andrena niveata* Friese, 1887 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
66. *Andrena nobilis* Morawitz, 1874 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Vorgin (1955). [DD]
67. *Andrena oralis* Morawitz, 1876 in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Vorgin (1955). [DD]

68. *Andrena ovatula* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Živojinović (1950); AZ coll.; also as *Andrena albofasciata* Thomson, 1871 in Lebedev (1931); as *Andrena afzeliella* (Kirby, 1802) in Petrik (1958). [NT]
69. *Andrena pandellei* Pérez, 1895 **New material examined:** 1 ♂; Novi Sad, Kamenički park; 45.2299°N, 19.8518°E; 20 Jun. 2018; A. Đukić leg.; Zsolt Józán det.; AÐ coll. [LC]
70. *Andrena paucisquama* Noskiewicz, 1924 **New material examined:** 1 ♀; Fruška gora, Manastir Grgeteg; 45.1383°N, 19.9044°E; 20 May 2018; S. Mudri-Stojnić leg.; Zsolt Józán det.; FSUNS. [DD]
71. *Andrena pilipes* Fabricius, 1781 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Petrik (1958); Vorgin (1918); Korlević (1890); ZM coll.; as *Andrena carbonaria* (Linnaeus, 1767) in Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
72. *Andrena polita* Smith, 1847 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
73. *Andrena potentillae* Panzer, 1809 in ZM coll. [DD]
74. *Andrena propinqua* Schenck, 1853 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); ZM coll. [DD]
75. *Andrena proxima* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Apfelbeck (1896). [DD]
76. **Andrena pyropygia* Kriechbaumer, 1873 in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
77. *Andrena rhenana* Stoeckert, 1930 in ZM coll. [DD]
78. *Andrena rosae* Panzer, 1801 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
79. *Andrena rufula* Schmiedeknecht, 1883 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
80. *Andrena schencki* Morawitz, 1866 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
81. *Andrena schlettereri* Friese, 1896 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
82. *Andrena scita* Eversmann, 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Vorgin (1955, 1918); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [DD]
83. *Andrena seminuda* Friese, 1896 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); as *Andrena setigera* Alfken, 1911 in Vorgin (1955). [DD]
84. *Andrena sericata* Imhoff, 1868 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Apfelbeck (1896). [DD]
85. *Andrena simillima* Smith, 1851 **New material examined:** 1 ♀; Vlasina, Delnice-Ljote; 42.6933°N, 22.3176°E; 22 Jul. 2019; A. Đukić leg.; Andrej Gogala det.; AÐ coll. [LC]
86. *Andrena simontornyella* Noskiewicz, 1939 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016). [LC]
87. *Andrena subopaca* Nylander, 1848 in Lebedev (1931); AÐ coll. [LC]
88. *Andrena suerinensis* Perkins 1914 in ZM coll. [DD]

89. *Andrena symphyti* Schmiedeknecht, 1883 in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); AZ coll.; ZM coll. [DD]
90. *Andrena taraxaci* Giraud, 1861 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Schwenninger (2015); Grozdanić (1971b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1965c); Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931); ZM coll. [DD]
91. *Andrena tarsata* Nylander, 1848 in Vorgin (1918); ZM coll. [DD]
92. *Andrena thoracica* (Fabricius, 1775) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [DD]
93. *Andrena tibialis* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Vorgin (1955); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
94. *Andrena trimmerana* (Kirby, 1802) in Lebedev (1931); ZM coll. [DD]
95. *Andrena truncatilabris* Morawitz, 1877 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Vorgin (1955, 1918); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [DD]
96. *Andrena ungeri* Mavromoustakis, 1952 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012). [LC]
97. *Andrena vaga* Panzer, 1799 in Lebedev (1931); ZM coll. [LC]
98. *Andrena variabilis* Smith, 1853 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931); AZ coll. [DD]
99. *Andrena varians* (Kirby, 1802) in Lebedev (1931); Vorgin (1955). [LC]
100. *Andrena ventralis* Imhoff, 1832 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
101. *Andrena ventricosa* Dours, 1873 in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Vorgin (1918). [DD]
102. *Andrena viridescens* Viereck, 1916 in Lebedev (1931); ZM coll. [DD]
103. *Andrena wilkella* (Kirby, 1802) in Vorgin (1955); as *Andrena convexiuscula* Kirby, 1802 in Petrik (1958); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [DD]

Camptopoeum Spinola, 1843 (2 species)

104. *Camptopoeum frontale* Fabricius 1804 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
105. *Camptopoeum friesei* Mocsáry 1894 in Grozdanić (1971b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

Clavipanurgus Warncke, 1972 (1 species)

106. *Clavipanurgus sculpturatus* Morawitz 1872 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]

Melitturga Latreille, 1809 (1 species)

107. *Melitturga clavicornis* Latreille 1808 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Petrik (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [NT]

Panurginus Nylander, 1848 (2 species)

108. *Panurginus labiatus* Eversmann 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
109. *≠Panurginus herzi* Morawitz, 1892 **New material examined:** 1 ♀; Vlasina, Vrtop; 42.7904°N, 22.372°E; 20 Jul. 2019; A. Đukić leg.; Andrej Gogala det.; AĐ coll. 1 ♀; Vlasina Rid; 42.7253°N, 22.3284°E; 22–23 Jul. 2019; A. Đukić leg.; Andrej Gogala det.; AĐ coll. [DD]

Panurgus Panzer, 1806 (2 species)

110. *≠Panurgus banksianus* Kirby 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); AĐ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]
111. *≠Panurgus calcaratus* Scopoli, 1763 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); AĐ coll.; as *Panurgus lobatus* (Panzer, 1799) in Petrik (1958). [LC]

Apidae (18 genera; 226 species)*Amegilla* Friese, 1897 (5 species)

112. *≠Amegilla albigena* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); ZM coll.; as *Anthophora albigena* Lepeletier, 1841 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgan (1955, 1918); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
113. *≠Amegilla garrula* Rossi, 1790 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); as *Anthophora garrula* Rossi, 1790 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); as *Anthophora garrulus* in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
114. *Amegilla magnilabris* (Fedtschenko 1875) as *Anthophora magnilabris* Fedtschenko, 1875 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
115. *≠Amegilla quadrifasciata* de Villers, 1789 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Stanisavljević (2000); ZM coll.; as *Anthophora quadrifasciata* (de Villers, 1789) in Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); as *Anthophora quadrifasciatus* in Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
116. *≠Amegilla salviae* Morawitz, 1876 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); ZM coll. [DD]

Ammobatooides Radoszkowski, 1867 (1 species)

117. *≠Ammobatooides abdominalis* (Eversmann, 1852) in ZM coll. [EN]

Ammobates Latreille, 1809 (2 species)

118. **Ammobates punctatus* (Fabricius, 1804) in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

119. **Ammobates vinctus* Gerstäcker, 1869 in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

Anthophora Latreille, 1803 (18 species)

120. *Anthophora aestivalis* Panzer 1801 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
121. ■*Anthophora atroalba* Lepeletier 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
122. ≠*Anthophora bimaculata* Panzer, 1798 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Vorgan (1918); ZM coll.; as *Saropoda bimaculata* in Petrik (1958); as *Anthophora bimaculatus* in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
123. ■*Anthophora canescens* Brullé 1832 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
124. *Anthophora crassipes* Lepeletier, 1841 in Lebedev (1931). [DD]
125. ■*Anthophora dalmatica* Pérez 1902 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
126. ■*Anthophora dufourii* Lepeletier 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
127. ≠*Anthophora fulvitaris* Brullé 1832 in ZM coll. [DD]
128. ≠*Anthophora furcata* Panzer, 1798 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); AÐ coll.; ZM coll.; as *Anthophora furcatus* in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
129. ■*Anthophora orientalis* Morawitz 1877 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
130. ≠*Anthophora plagiata* Illiger, 1806 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Anthophora parietina* (Fabricius, 1793) in Mučalica (1987a, 1987b); Grozdanić (1971b); Grozdanić and Stevanović (1965); Grozdanić and Vasić (1965b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgan (1918); ZM coll.; *Anthophora parietinus* in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
131. ≠*Anthophora plumipes* Pallas, 1772 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); AÐ coll.; ZM coll.; as *Anthophora acervorum* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Grozdanić (1971b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1965b, 1965c); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
132. *Anthophora podagra* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Anthophora podagrus* in Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
133. ≠*Anthophora pubescens* Fabricius 1781 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Grozdanić and Radivojević (1972); Grozdanić (1971b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); SG coll. [DD]
134. *Anthophora quadrimaculata* Panzer, 1798 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Anthophora vulpina* (Panzer, 1798) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); as *Anthophora vulpinus* Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
135. ≠*Anthophora retusa* Linnaeus, 1758 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); ZM coll.; as *Anthophora retusus* in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
136. ■*Anthophora robusta* Klug 1845 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
137. ≠*Anthophora salviae* (Panzer, 1804) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Vorgan (1955, 1918); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Korlević (1890); also as *Anthophora crinipes* Smith, 1854 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); as *Anthophora crin-*

ipes in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mučalica (1997, 1990, 1987b); Grozdanić (1971b); Grozdanić and Mučalica (1969); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a, 1965b); AĐ coll.; ZM coll. [DD]

Apis Linnaeus, 1768 (1 species)

138. ≠*Apis mellifera* Linnaeus 1758 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Kulinčević et al. (1997); Krunić (1994, 1986); Grozdanić (1970, 1958b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a); Petrik (1958); Vlatković (1957); Živojinović (1950); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); AĐ coll.; ZM coll. [DD]

Biastes Panzer, 1806 (3 species)

139. ≠*Biastes brevicornis* (Panzer, 1798) in Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); SG coll. [LC]
 140. *Biastes emarginatus* (Schenck, 1853) in Vorgin (1918). [LC]
 141. ■*Biastes truncatus* (Nylander, 1848) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [VU]

Bombus Latreille, 1802 (47 species)

142. ≠*Bombus argillaceus* (Scopoli, 1763) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rasmont et al. (2015); Grozdanić (1971b, 1970); Grozdanić and Vasić (1965c); Grozdanić and Čolović (1955b); Lebedev (1931); ZM coll. [LC]
 143. ■*Bombus armeniacus* Radoszkowski, 1877 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [EN]
 144. ≠*Bombus barbutellus* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rasmont et al. (2015); SG coll.; as *Psithyrus barbutellus* (Kirby, 1802) in Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a); Vorgin (1955); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
 145. *Bombus bohemicus* Seidl, 1838 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rasmont et al. (2015). [LC]
 146. ≠*Bombus campestris* Panzer, 1801 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rasmont et al. (2015); AĐ coll.; as *Psithyrus campestris* f. *francisanus* K. and also as *Psithyrus campestris* f. *rosiellus* K. in Vorgin (1955). [LC]
 147. *Bombus confusus* Schenck, 1861 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rasmont et al. (2015); Mocsáry (1897). [VU]
 148. ■*Bombus cryptarum* Fabricius, 1775 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
 149. *Bombus cullumanus* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Bombus serisquama* Morawitz, 1888 in Lebedev (1931). [CR]
 150. *Bombus deuteronymus* Schulz, 1879 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rasmont et al. (2015); as *Bombus bureschi* Pittioni, 1939 in Živojinović (1950). [DD]
 151. ■*Bombus distinguendus* Morawitz, 1869 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [VU]
 152. ■*Bombus flavidus* Eversmann, 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]

153. *Bombus fragrans* (Pallas, 1771) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mocsáry (1897). [EN]
154. ■ *Bombus gerstaeckeri* Morawitz, 1881 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [VU]
155. ≠ *Bombus haematurus* Kriechbaumer, 1870 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rasmont et al. (2015); Grozdanić (1971b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1965c); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); ZM coll. [LC]
156. ≠ *Bombus hortorum* Linnaeus, 1761 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rasmont et al. (2015); Grozdanić (1971b, 1970); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a); Grozdanić and Vasić (1965c); Grozdanić and Baranov (1963); Vorgan (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Apfelbeck (1896); AĐ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]
157. ≠ *Bombus humilis* Illiger, 1806 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Rasmont et al. (2015); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a, 1965c); Živojinović (1950); AĐ coll.; ZM coll.; as *Bombus helferanus* Seidl, 1838 in Vorgan (1955); Lebedev (1931); as *Bombus variabilis* Schmiedeknecht, 1878 in Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
158. ≠ *Bombus hypnorum* Linnaeus, 1758 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Rasmont et al. (2015); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); AĐ coll. [LC]
159. ■ *Bombus jonellus* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
160. *Bombus laesus* Morawitz, 1875 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Vorgan (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [NT]
161. ≠ *Bombus lapidarius* Linnaeus, 1758 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Rasmont et al. (2015); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Grozdanić (1971b, 1970); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a, 1965c); Vorgan (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); AĐ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]
162. ≠ *Bombus lucorum* Linnaeus, 1761 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Vorgan (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); AĐ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]
163. ■ *Bombus mendax* Gerstäcker, 1869 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
164. ■ *Bombus mesomelas* Gerstäcker, 1869 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
165. ■ *Bombus mlokosievitzii* Radoszkowski, 1877 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
166. ■ *Bombus mocsaryi* Kriechbaumer, 1877 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [EN]
167. ■ *Bombus monticola* Smith, 1849 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
168. ■ *Bombus mucidus* Gerstäcker, 1869 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
169. *Bombus muscorum* Linnaeus, 1758 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stevanović and Lazarov (1977); Vorgan (1955). [VU]
170. *Bombus niveatus* Kriechbaumer, 1870 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rasmont et al. (2015); as *Bombus vorticosus* Gerstäcker, 1872 in Vorgan (1955). [LC]
171. ■ *Bombus norvegicus* Sparre-Schneider, 1918 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
172. ≠ *Bombus pascuorum* Scopoli, 1763 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rasmont et al. (2015); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); AĐ coll.; ZM coll.; as *Bombus cognatus* Stephens, 1846

- in Grozdanić (1971b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1965c); Lebedev (1931); Vorgin (1918); as *Bombus agrorum* (Fabricius, 1787) in Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a, 1965c); Grozdanić (1960); Grozdanić and Stevanović (1959); Petrik (1958); Grozdanić and Čolović (1955a, 1955b); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); Korlević (1890). [LC]
173. *♂Bombus pomorum* Panzer, 1805 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rasmont et al. (2015); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); AÐ coll. [VU]
174. *♂Bombus pratorum* Linnaeus, 1761 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Rasmont et al. (2015); Grozdanić and Čolović (1955a, 1955b); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); AÐ coll. [LC]
175. *Bombus pyrenaicus* Pérez, 1879 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rasmont et al. (2015). [LC]
176. *♂Bombus quadricolor* Lepeletier, 1832 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rasmont et al. (2015); AÐ coll. [LC]
177. *♂Bombus ruderarius* Müller, 1776 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Rasmont et al. (2015); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); AÐ coll.; as *Bombus derhamellus* (Kirby, 1802) in Lebedev (1931); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
178. *Bombus ruderatus* Fabricius, 1775 in Petrik (1958); Vorgin (1955). [LC]
179. *♂Bombus rupestris* Fabricius, 1793 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rasmont et al. (2015); AÐ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]
180. *♂Bombus sichelii* Radoszkowski, 1859 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
181. *♂Bombus soroensis* Fabricius, 1776 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rasmont et al. (2015); Vorgin (1955); ZM coll.; as *Bombus proteus* Gerstäcker, 1869 in Lebedev (1931). [LC]
182. *Bombus subterraneus* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rasmont et al. (2015). [LC]
183. *♂Bombus sylvarum* Linnaeus, 1761 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Rasmont et al. (2015); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Grozdanić (1971b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a, 1965c); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); Korlević (1890); SG coll. [LC]
184. *♂Bombus sylvestris* Lepeletier, 1832 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rasmont et al. (2015); AÐ coll. [LC]
185. *♂Bombus terrestris* Linnaeus, 1758 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rasmont et al. (2015); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Grozdanić (1971b, 1970); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a, 1965c); Grozdanić and Baranov (1963); Petrik (1958); Grozdanić and Čolović (1955b); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Apfelbeck (1896); AÐ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]
186. *♂Bombus vestalis* Geoffroy, 1785 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rasmont et al. (2015); AÐ coll.; SG coll.; as *Psithyrus vestalis* Geoffroy, 1785 in Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a); Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]

187. *≠Bombus wurflenii* Radoszkowski, 1859 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rasmont et al. (2015); AĐ coll.; as *Bombus mastrucatus* Gerstäcker, 1869 in Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
188. *Bombus zonatus* Smith, 1854 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897). [EN]

Ceratina Latreille, 1802 (11 species)

189. *≠Ceratina acuta* Friese, 1896 in Grozdanić (1971b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); ZM coll. [LC]
190. *≠Ceratina callosa* Fabricius, 1794 in Grozdanić (1971b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); ZM coll. [LC]
191. *≠Ceratina chalcites* Germar, 1839 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Vorigin (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
192. *≠Ceratina chalybea* Chevrier, 1872 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016). [LC]
193. *≠Ceratina cucurbitina* Rossi, 1792 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Grozdanić (1971b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); ZM coll. [LC]
194. *≠Ceratina cyanea* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); AĐ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]
195. *▪Ceratina dallatorreana* Friese, 1896 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
196. *▪Ceratina dentiventris* Gerstäcker, 1869 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
197. *≠Ceratina loewi* Gerstäcker, 1869 in ZM coll. [DD]
198. *Ceratina nigroaenea* Gerstäcker, 1869 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
199. *≠Ceratina nigrolabiata* Friese, 1896 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Grozdanić (1971b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); AĐ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]

Epeoloides Giraud, 1863 (1 species)

200. *≠Epeoloides coecutiens* (Fabricius, 1775) **New material examined:** 1 ♂, 1 ♀; Vlasina, Blato, Božički kanal; 42.6786°N, 22.3543°E; 23 Jul. 2019; T. Tot, N. Veljković leg.; Andrej Gogala det.; AĐ coll. [LC]

Epeolus Latreille, 1802 (5 species)

201. *Epeolus cruciger* Panzer, 1799 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Bogusch and Hadrava (2018); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [NT]
202. *Epeolus fasciatus* Friese, 1895 in Bogusch and Hadrava (2018); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]

203. *≠Epeolus schummeli* Schilling, 1849 in SG coll. [NT]
204. *Epeolus transitorius* Eversmann, 1852 in Bogusch and Hadrava (2018); Petrik (1958); as *Epeolus julliani* Pérez, 1884 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). Note: According to Bogusch and Hadrava (2018) *E. julliani* is syn. nov. under *E. transitorius*. [DD]
205. *≠Epeolus variegatus* Linnaeus, 1758 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Bogusch and Hadrava (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Petrik (1958); Apfelbeck (1896); also as *Epeolus productus* Thomson, 1870 in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

Eucera Scopoli, 1770 (33 species)

206. *Eucera alternans* Brullé, 1832 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Tetralonia ruficollis* (Brullé, 1832) in Petrik (1958); as *Eucera ruficollis* (Brullé, 1832) in Vorgin (1918). [DD]
207. *Eucera caspica* Morawitz, 1873 in Vorgin (1918). [LC]
208. *≠Eucera chrysopyga* Pérez, 1854 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
209. *≠Eucera cineraria* Eversmann, 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016). [LC]
210. *≠Eucera clypeata* Erichson, 1835 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Lebedev (1931); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); also as *Eucera similis* Lepeletier, 1841 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
211. *Eucera dalmatica* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
212. *≠Eucera excisa* Mocsáry, 1879 in Grozdanić (1971b, 1969a); Grozdanić and Vasić (1967b); Vorgin (1918); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); ZM coll. [DD]
213. *≠Eucera hungarica* Friese, 1896 in Mocsáry (1897); SG coll.; also as *Tetralonia hungarica* (Friese, 1896) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
214. *≠Eucera interrupta* Bär, 1850 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
215. *≠Eucera longicornis* Linnaeus, 1758 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); AĐ coll.; SG coll.; ZM coll.; also as *Eucera difficilis* Pérez, 1879 in Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
216. *≠Eucera nigrescens* Pérez, 1879 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); ZM coll.; as *Eucera tuberculata* (Fabricius, 1793) in Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a, 1965c); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
217. *≠Eucera nigrifacies* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

218. *≠Eucera pollinaris* Kirby, 1802 in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); as *Eucera armeniaca* (Morawitz, 1877) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [DD]
219. *Eucera proxima* Morawitz, 1875 as *Eucera nitidiventris* Mocsáry, 1879 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1918); Apfelbeck (1896). [DD]
220. *▪Eucera punctulata* Alfken, 1942 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
221. *≠Eucera seminuda* Brullé, 1832 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Lebedev (1931); Vorgin (1918); ZM coll. [LC]
222. *≠Eucera taurica* Morawitz, 1871 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016). [DD]
223. *Eucera tricincta* Erichson, 1835 in Vorgin (1918); also as *Tetralonia tricincta* (Erichson, 1835) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
224. *▪Eucera vittulata* Noskiewicz, 1934 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
225. *Eucera vulpes* Brullé, 1832 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Eucera parvula* Friese, 1896 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [DD]
- Note: According to Dorchin et al. (2018), genera *Cubitalia* Friese, 1911, *Tetralonia* Spinola, 1838 and *Tetraloniella* Ashmead, 1899 are placed as subgenera within *Eucera* Scopoli, 1770 (and *Tetraloniella* is synonymised with *Tetralonia*):
226. *≠Eucera (Cubitalia) parvicornis* Mocsáry, 1878 as *Cubitalia parvicornis* in ZM coll.; as *Eucera parvicornis* Mocsáry, 1878 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
227. *≠Eucera (Tetralonia) malvae* Rossi, 1790 as *Tetralonia malvae* in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Grozdanić (1971b); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); ZM coll.; also as *Eucera malvae* (Rossi, 1790) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); as *Eucera malvae* in Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
228. *≠Eucera (Tetralonia) alticincta* Lepeletier, 1841 as *Tetraloniella alticincta* in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); as *Tetralonia alticincta* (Lepeletier, 1841) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012). [LC]
229. *≠Eucera (Tetralonia) dentata* Germar, 1839 as *Tetraloniella dentata* in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Tetralonia dentata* (Klug, 1835) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Lebedev (1931); as *Eucera dentata* Germar, 1839 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
230. *Eucera (Tetralonia) fulvescens* Giraud, 1863 as *Tetraloniella fulvescens* in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Tetralonia dufouri* (Pérez, 1879) in Vorgin (1955). [DD]
231. *▪Eucera (Tetralonia) glauca* Fabricius 1775 as *Tetraloniella glauca* in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
232. *≠Eucera (Tetralonia) graja* (Eversmann, 1852) as *Tetraloniella graja* in Grozdanić (1971b); ZM coll. [DD]
233. *≠Eucera (Tetralonia) lyncea* Mocsáry, 1879 as *Tetraloniella lyncea* in Markov (2017); as *Tetralonia lyncea* Mocsáry, 1879 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Grozdanić (1971b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966b); Lebedev (1931); SG coll.; ZM coll.; as *Eucera lyncea* (Mocsáry, 1879) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
234. *≠Eucera (Tetralonia) nana* Morawitz, 1874 as *Tetraloniella nana* in Markov (2017); ZM coll.; as *Tetralonia nana* Morawitz, 1874 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018);

- Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Grozdanić (1971b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1967a); Lebedev (1931); SG coll.; as *Eucera nana* (Morawitz, 1874) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
235. *♂Eucera (Tetralonia) ruficornis* Fabricius, 1804 as *Eucera ruficornis* Fabricius, 1804 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897); as *Tetralonia ruficornis* (Fabricius, 1804) in Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931); SG coll. [DD]
236. *♂Eucera (Tetralonia) pollinosa* Lepeletier, 1841 as *Tetralonia pollinosa* (Lepeletier, 1841) and also as *Eucera pollinosa* Lepeletier, 1841 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); as *Eucera pollinosa* in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897); as *Macrocera fossulata* in Korlević (1890). [DD]
237. *♂Eucera (Tetralonia) salicariae* Lepeletier, 1841 as *Eucera salicariae* (Lepeletier, 1841) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); as *Tetralonia salicariae* (Lepeletier, 1841) in Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950); SG coll.; ZM coll. [DD]
238. *♂Eucera (Tetralonia) scabiosae* Mocsáry, 1881 as *Tetraloniella scabiosae* in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); as *Tetralonia scabiosae* (Mocsáry, 1881) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Grozdanić (1971b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); SG coll. ZM coll.; as *Eucera scabiosae* Mocsáry, 1881 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955, 1918); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]

Habropoda Smith, 1854 (2 species)

239. *♂Habropoda tarsata* Spinola, 1838 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
240. *♂Habropoda zonatula* Smith, 1854 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]

Melecta Latreille, 1802 (7 species)

241. *♂Melecta albifrons* Förster, 1771 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Melecta armata* (Panzer, 1799) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1918); ZM coll. [LC]
242. *♂Melecta duodecimmaculata* Rossi 1790 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
243. *♂Melecta fulgida* Lieftinck, 1980 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
244. *♂Melecta funeraria* Smith, 1854 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
245. *♂Melecta italica* Radoszkowski, 1876 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
246. *♂Melecta luctuosa* Scopoli, 1770 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Vorgin (1918); ZM coll. [LC]
247. *♂Melecta obscura* Friese, 1895 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]

Nomada Scopoli, 1770 (77 species)

248. *Nomada alboguttata* Herrich-Schäffer, 1839 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
249. *Nomada alpigena* Schwarz, Gusenleitner, & Mazzucco, 1999 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). Note: There are no type specimens listed from Serbia in Schwarz, Gusenleitner and Mazzucco (1999). [DD]

250. *Nomada argentata* Herrich-Schäffer, 1839 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018). [NT]
251. *Nomada armata* Herrich-Schäffer, 1839 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); AÐ coll. [NT]
252. *Nomada atroscutellaris* Strand, 1921 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018). [LC]
253. *Nomada basalis* Herrich-Schäffer, 1839 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); as *Nomada tripunctata* Morawitz, 1872 in Vorgan (1955, 1918); as *Nomada flavomaculata* Lucas, 1849 in Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
254. *Nomada bifasciata* Olivier, 1811 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); as *Nomada pusilla* in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
255. *Nomada bispinosa* Mocsáry, 1883 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
256. *Nomada bluethgeni* Stoeckert, 1943 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016). [LC]
257. *Nomada braunsiana* Schmiedeknecht, 1882 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931). [NT]
258. *Nomada calimorpha* Schmiedeknecht, 1882 in Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
259. *Nomada castellana* Dusmety Alonso, 1913 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
260. *Nomada confinis* Schmiedeknecht, 1882 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
261. *Nomada conjungens* Herrich-Schäffer, 1839 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
262. *Nomada cruenta* Schmiedeknecht, 1882 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Vorgan (1918). [LC]
263. *Nomada distinguenda* Morawitz, 1874 in Smit (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgan (1918); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
264. *Nomada emarginata* Morawitz, 1877 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
265. *Nomada errans* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Lebedev (1931). [NT]
266. *Nomada erythrocephala* Morawitz, 1870 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [DD]
267. *Nomada fabriciana* Linnaeus, 1767 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931); AÐ coll. [LC]
268. *Nomada facilis* Schwarz, 1967 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
269. *Nomada femoralis* Morawitz, 1869 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgan (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
270. *Nomada ferruginata* Linné 1767 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgan (1955, 1918); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
271. *Nomada flava* Panzer, 1798 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Lebedev (1931); AÐ coll. [LC]

272. *Nomada flavoguttata* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Apfelbeck (1896); AÐ coll. [LC]
273. *Nomada flavopicta* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
274. *Nomada fucata* Panzer, 1798 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); AÐ coll.; as *Nomada varia* Panzer, 1798 in Petrik (1958). [LC]
275. *Nomada fulvicornis* Fabricius, 1793 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); also as *Nomada lineola* Panzer, 1798 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); as *Nomada lineola* in Vorgin (1955); Mocsáry (1897); as *Nomada robusta* Morawitz, 1870 in Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
276. *Nomada furva* Panzer, 1798 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [DD]
277. *Nomada furvoides* Stoeckhert, 1944 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
278. *Nomada fuscicornis* Nylander, 1848 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Vorgin (1918). [LC]
279. *Nomada goodeniana* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
280. *Nomada gribodoi* Schmiedeknecht, 1882 as *Nomada elegans* Mocsáry, 1897 in Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
281. *Nomada guttulata* Schenck, 1861 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Vorgin (1918). [LC]
282. *Nomada hirtipes* Pérez, 1884 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
283. *Nomada hungarica* Dalla Torre & Friese, 1894 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [DD]
284. *Nomada immaculata* Morawitz, 1874 in Vorgin (1918). [DD]
285. *Nomada incisa* Schmiedeknecht, 1882 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
286. *Nomada integra* Brullé, 1832 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); AÐ coll. [LC]
287. *Nomada kobli* Schmiedeknecht, 1882 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
288. *Nomada lathburiana* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); SG coll. [LC]
289. *Nomada leucophthalma* (Kirby, 1802) **New material examined:** 1 ♀; Vlasi-na, Veliki čemernik; 42.7368°N, 22.2723°E; 25 May 2019; M. Vujić leg.; Andrej Gogala det.; AÐ coll. [LC]
290. *Nomada marshamella* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018). [LC]
291. *Nomada mauritanica* Lepeletier, 1841 in Smit (2018); as *Nomada chrysopyga* Morawitz, 1871 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
292. *Nomada mocsaryi* Schmiedeknecht, 1882 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
293. *Nomada moeschleri* Alfken, 1913 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]

294. *Nomada mutabilis* Morawitz, 1870 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Vorgin (1918); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
295. *Nomada mutica* Morawitz, 1872 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931). [NT]
296. *Nomada nobilis* Herrich-Schäffer, 1839 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
297. *Nomada numida* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018). [LC]
298. ■ *Nomada obtusifrons* Nylander, 1848 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
299. ■ *Nomada opaca* Alfken, 1913 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
300. ■ *Nomada pallispinosa* Schwarz, 1967 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
301. *Nomada panzeri* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018). [LC]
302. *Nomada pectoralis* Morawitz, 1877 in Vorgin (1918). [DD]
303. *Nomada piccioliana* Magretti, 1883 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018). [LC]
304. *Nomada pleurosticta* Herrich-Schäffer, 1839 as *Nomada major* Morawitz, 1872 in Lebedev (1931). [NT]
305. ■ *Nomada propinqua* Schmiedeknecht, 1882 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
306. *Nomada pulchra* Arnold, 1888 in Smit (2018). [EN]
307. *Nomada rhenana* Morawitz, 1872 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [NT]
308. ≠ *Nomada ruficornis* Linnaeus, 1758 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Apfelbeck (1896); Mocsáry (1897); AÐ coll; also as *Nomada bifida* Thomson, 1872 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); as *Nomada bifida* in Lebedev (1931). [LC]
309. *Nomada rufipes* Fabricius, 1793 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
310. *Nomada sexfasciata* Panzer, 1799 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
311. ■ *Nomada sheppardana* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
312. *Nomada signata* Jurine, 1807 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
313. *Nomada similis* Morawitz, 1872 in Vorgin (1918). [LC]
314. *Nomada stigma* Fabricius, 1804 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Nomada austriaca* Schmiedeknecht, 1882 in Vorgin (1918). [LC]
315. *Nomada striata* Fabricius, 1793 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Nomada ochrosoma* (Kirby, 1802) in Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
316. ■ *Nomada succincta* Panzer, 1798 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
317. ■ *Nomada symphyti* Stoeckhert, 1930 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
318. *Nomada tenella* Mocsáry, 1883 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018). [NT]
319. *Nomada transitoria* Schmiedeknecht, 1882 in Smit (2018). [LC]
320. ■ *Nomada tridentirostris* Dours, 1873 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
321. *Nomada trispinosa* Schmiedeknecht, 1882 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
322. ■ *Nomada verna* Schmiedeknecht, 1882 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]

323. *Nomada villosa* Thomson, 1870 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931). [NT]
324. *Nomada zonata* Panzer, 1798 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Smit (2018); Lebedev (1931); Vorgin (1918). [LC]

Pasites Jurine, 1807 (1 species)

325. *Pasites maculatus* Jurine, 1807 in Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

Thyreus Panzer, 1806 (7 species)

326. *Thyreus affinis* Morawitz, 1874 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Crocisa affinis* Morawitz, 1874 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [DD]
327. ≠ *Thyreus histrionicus* Illiger, 1806 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); ZM coll.; as *Crocisa major* Morawitz, 1875 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
328. ≠ *Thyreus orbatus* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); ZM coll. [LC]
329. ■ *Thyreus picaron* Lieftinck, 1968 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
330. ≠ *Thyreus ramosus* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); ZM coll.; as *Crocisa ramosa* Lepeletier, 1841 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
331. ≠ *Thyreus scutellaris* Fabricius, 1781 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); ZM coll.; as *Crocisa scutellaris* (Fabricius, 1781) in Petrik (1958); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
332. *Thyreus truncatus* Pérez, 1883 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Crocisa truncata* Pérez, 1883 in Mocsáry (1897). [DD]

Triepeolus Robertson, 1901 (1 species)

333. **Triepeolus tristis* (Smith, 1854) as *Epeolus tristis* Smith, 1854 in Mocsáry (1897). [NT]

Xylocopa Latreille, 1802 (4 species)

334. ≠ *Xylocopa iris* Christ, 1791 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); ZM coll.; as *Xylocopa cyanescens* Brullé, 1832 in Grozdanić and Mučalica (1973); Grozdanić (1971b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
335. ■ *Xylocopa olivieri* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
336. ≠ *Xylocopa valga* Gerstäcker, 1872 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Grozdanić and Mučalica (1973); Grozdanić (1971b, 1970, 1950b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1965c); Grozdanić and Baranov (1963); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Grozdanić and Čolović (1955b); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); AÐ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]

337. *Xylocopa violacea* Linnaeus, 1758 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Grozdanić and Mučalica (1973); Grozdanić (1971b, 1950b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Apfelbeck (1896); AÐ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]

Colletidae (2 genera; 69 species)

Colletes Latreille, 1802 (27 species)

338. *Colletes albomaculatus* (Lucas, 1849) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
339. *Colletes anchusae* Noskiewicz, 1924 Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a); ZM coll. [EN]
340. *Colletes brevigena* Noskiewicz, 1936 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Burger (2010). [LC]
341. *Colletes carinatus* Radoszkowski, 1891 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
342. *Colletes caskanus* (Strand, 1919) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
343. *Colletes chengtshensis* Yasumatsu, 1935 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [VU]
344. *Colletes cunicularius* (Linnaeus, 1761) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Grozdanić (1971b, 1958a); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897); AÐ coll.; ZM coll.; as *Colletes cunicularia* in Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
345. *Colletes daviesanus* Smith, 1846 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); AÐ coll.; as *Colletes daviesana* in Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
346. *Colletes eous* Morice, 1904 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
347. *Colletes floralis* Eversmann, 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [VU]
348. *Colletes fodiens* (Fourcroy, 1785) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [VU]
349. *Colletes foveolaris* Pérez, 1903 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
350. *Colletes gallicus* Radoszkowski, 1891 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
351. *Colletes graeffei* Alfken, 1900 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [EN]
352. *Colletes hederæ* Schmidt & Westrich, 1993 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Burger (2010). [LC]
353. *Colletes hylaeiformis* Eversmann, 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vargin (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
354. *Colletes inexpectatus* Noskiewicz, 1936 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
355. *Colletes maidli* Noskiewicz, 1936 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017). [LC]
356. *Colletes marginatus* Smith, 1846 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); as *Colletes marginata* in Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
357. *Colletes meyeri* Noskiewicz, 1936 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [EN]
358. *Colletes mlkossewiczii* Radoszkowski, 1891 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]

359. *≠Colletes nasutus* Smith, 1853 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897). [EN]
360. *▪Colletes nigricans* Gistel, 1857 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
361. *Colletes punctatus* Mocsáry, 1877 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [EN]
362. *▪Colletes senilis* (Eversmann, 1852) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
363. *Colletes succinctus* (Linnaeus, 1785) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Vorgin (1918). [NT]
364. *≠Colletes similis* Schenck, 1853 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); as *Colletes picistigma* Thomson, 1872 in Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

Hylaeus Fabricius, 1793 (42 species)

365. *▪Hylaeus adriaticus* (Warncke, 1972) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
366. *▪Hylaeus alpinus* (Morawitz, 1867) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
367. *Hylaeus angustatus* (Schenck, 1861) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Prosopis angustata* Schenck, 1861 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950). [LC]
368. *≠Hylaeus annularis* (Kirby, 1802) in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); AÐ coll.; as *Prosopis annularis* (Kirby, 1802) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950). Note: It is difficult to be certain about the correct status of specimens in the literature before Notton and Dathe (2008) who pointed out the confusion regarding previously understood interpretation of the name. [DD]
369. *Hylaeus annulatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Prosopis annulata* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
370. *≠Hylaeus brevicornis* Nylander, 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); as *Prosopis brevicornis* (Nylander, 1852) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
371. *▪Hylaeus clypearis* (Schenck, 1853) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
372. *≠Hylaeus communis* Nylander, 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); AÐ coll.; as *Prosopis communis* (Nylander, 1852) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
373. *≠Hylaeus confusus* Nylander, 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); AÐ coll.; as *Prosopis confusa* (Nylander, 1852) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
374. *▪Hylaeus coriaceus* (Pérez, 1895) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
375. *≠Hylaeus cornutus* Curtis, 1831 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); as *Prosopis cornuta* (Curtis, 1831) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955, 1918); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

376. ■ *Hylaeus crassanus* (Warncke, 1972) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
377. *Hylaeus difformis* (Eversmann, 1852) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Prosopis difformis* Eversmann, 1852 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
378. *Hylaeus dilatatus* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Prosopis dilatata* (Kirby, 1802) in Apfelbeck (1896). Note: It is difficult to be certain about the correct status of specimens in the literature before Notton and Dathe (2008) who pointed out the confusion regarding previously understood interpretation of the name. [LC]
379. *Hylaeus duckei* (Alfken, 1904) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Prosopis duckei* Alfken, 1904 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [DD]
380. *Hylaeus euryscapus* Förster, 1871 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Prosopis euryscapus* (Förster, 1871) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); *Prosopis euryscapa* in Vorgin (1955, 1918); Mocsáry (1897). Note: It is difficult to be certain about the correct status of specimens in the literature before Notton and Dathe (2008) who pointed out the confusion regarding previously understood interpretation of the name *H. annularis*. [DD]
381. *Hylaeus gibbus* Saunders, 1850 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Prosopis gibba* (Saunders, 1850) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
382. ■ *Hylaeus greddleri* Förster, 1871 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
383. *Hylaeus hyalinatus* Smith, 1842 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Prosopis hyalinata* Smith, 1842 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
384. ■ *Hylaeus hyperpunctatus* (Strand, 1909) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
385. ■ *Hylaeus imparilis* Förster, 1871 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
386. *Hylaeus incongruus* Förster, 1871 as *Prosopis genalis* Thoms. in Vorgin (1918). [DD]
387. ■ *Hylaeus kabri* Förster, 1871 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
388. *Hylaeus leptcephalus* (Morawitz, 1870) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Prosopis bisinuata* Förster, 1871 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
389. ≠ *Hylaeus lineolatus* (Schenck, 1861) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); AÐ coll.; ZM coll.; as *Prosopis lineolata* Schenck, 1861 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
390. *Hylaeus meridionalis* Förster, 1871 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Prosopis meridionalis* Förster, 1871 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
391. ≠ *Hylaeus nigrinus* (Fabricius, 1798) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); AÐ coll.; as *Prosopis nigrina* (Fabricius, 1798) in Lebedev (1931). [LC]
392. ■ *Hylaeus nivaliformis* Dathe, 1977 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
393. ■ *Hylaeus pfankuchi* (Alfken, 1919) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
394. *Hylaeus pictipes* Nylander, 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Prosopis pictipes* (Nylander, 1852) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1918). [LC]
395. *Hylaeus punctatus* (Brullé, 1832) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Prosopis punctata* Brullé, 1832 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]

396. ■ *Hylaeus punctulatissimus* Smith, 1842 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
 397. ■ *Hylaeus punctus* Förster, 1871 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
 398. ■ *Hylaeus rugicollis* Morawitz, 1873 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
 399. ■ *Hylaeus scutellatus* (Spinola, 1838) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
 400. *Hylaeus signatus* (Panzer, 1798) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Prosopis pratensis* (Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgan (1955); as *Prosopis bipunctata* (Fabricius, 1798) in Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
 401. *Hylaeus sinuatus* (Schenck, 1853) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Petrik (1958); as *Prosopis minuta* (Fabricius, 1793) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); as *Prosopis sinuata* (Schenck, 1853) in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
 402. ■ *Hylaeus soror* (Pérez, 1903) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
 403. *Hylaeus styriacus* Förster, 1871 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Prosopis styriaca* (Förster, 1871) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [DD]
 404. ■ *Hylaeus taeniolatus* Förster, 1871 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
 405. ■ *Hylaeus tyrolensis* Förster, 1871 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
 406. *Hylaeus variegatus* (Fabricius, 1798) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Prosopis variegata* (Fabricius, 1798) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]

Halictidae (12 genera; 138 species)

Ceylalictus Strand, 1913 (1 species)

407. *Ceylalictus variegatus* (Olivier, 1789) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Nomioides jucunda* Morawitz, 1874 in Petrik (1958); as *Nomioides variegatus* (Olivier, 1789) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

Dufourea Lepeletier, 1841 (4 species)

408. **Dufourea alpina* Morawitz, 1865 in Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
 409. *Dufourea dentiventris* (Nylander, 1848) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictoides dentiventris* Nylander, 1848 in Lebedev (1931). [NT]
 410. ♂ *Dufourea inermis* (Nylander, 1848) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); AÐ coll. [NT]
 411. ■ *Dufourea minuta* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]

Halictus Latreille, 1804 (18 species)

412. ♂ *Halictus asperulus* Pérez, 1895 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Grozdanić (1972a); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
 413. ♂ *Halictus brunnescens* (Eversmann, 1852) in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016). [DD]
 414. ■ *Halictus carinthiacus* Blüthgen, 1936 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [EN]

415. *Halictus cochlearitarsis* Dours, 1872 in Grozdanić (1966); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
416. ~~*Halictus compressus*~~ (Walkenaer, 1802) as *Halictus eurygnathus* Blüthgen, 1930 in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Živojinović (1950). [LC]
417. ~~*Halictus fulvipes*~~ (Klug, 1817) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mučalica (1968); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
418. ~~*Halictus langobardicus*~~ Blüthgen, 1944 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
419. ~~*Halictus maculatus*~~ Smith, 1848 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Grozdanić (1972a); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); Korlević (1890); AÐ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]
420. *Halictus mucoreus* Eversmann, 1852 in Vorgin (1955, 1918); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
421. ~~*Halictus patellatus*~~ Morawitz, 1873 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); AZ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]
422. ~~*Halictus quadricinctus*~~ (Fabricius, 1776) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Grozdanić (1971b, 1966); Vasić (1967); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a, 1965c); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Anđelković (1949); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); as *Halictus quadristrigatus* Latreille, 1805 in Petrik (1958); Vorgin (1955); Korlević (1890). [NT]
423. *Halictus resurgens* Nurse, 1903 as *Halictus holtzi* Schulz, 1906 in Lebedev (1931). [LC]
424. ~~*Halictus rubicundus*~~ (Christ, 1791) in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); AÐ coll.; as *Halictus quadrifasciatus* Smith, 1870 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018). [LC]
425. ~~*Halictus sajoi*~~ Blüthgen, 1923 in Grozdanić (1971a); ZM coll.; as *Halictus veneticus* Móczár, 1967 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [DD]
426. ~~*Halictus scabiosae*~~ (Rossi, 1790) in Vasić (1979a); Grozdanić (1971b, 1970, 1966, 1960); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a, 1965c); Krunić (1959); Vorgin (1955); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); ZM coll.; FSUNS. [LC]
427. ~~*Halictus sexcinctus*~~ (Fabricius, 1775) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Grozdanić (1960, 1950a); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Apfelbeck (1896); Mocsáry (1897); Korlević (1890); AZ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]
428. ~~*Halictus simplex*~~ Blüthgen, 1923 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); AÐ coll.; AZ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]

429. *Halictus tetrazonius* (Klug, 1817) in Petrik (1958); Vorgan (1955); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); SG coll.; ZM coll. [DD]

Lasioglossum Curtis, 1833 (72 species)

430. *Lasioglossum aeratum* (Kirby, 1802) as *Halictus viridiaeneus* Blüthgen, 1918 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgan (1955); as *Halictus aeratus* (Kirby, 1802) in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
431. *Lasioglossum albipes* (Fabricius, 1781) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); as *Halictus albipes* (Fabricius, 1781) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); as *Halictus obovatus* Kirby in Petrik (1958). [LC]
432. *Lasioglossum alpigenum* (Dalla Torre, 1877) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
433. *Lasioglossum angusticeps* (Perkins, 1895) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
434. *Lasioglossum apostoli* Ebmer, 1970 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
435. *Lasioglossum bischoffi* (Blüthgen, 1931) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus bischoffi* Blüthgen, 1931 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [DD]
436. *Lasioglossum brevicorne* (Schenck, 1868) in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); AĐ coll.; ZM coll.; as *Halictus brevicornis* Schenck, 1870 ["1869"] in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgan (1955). [NT]
437. *Lasioglossum calceatum* (Scopoli, 1763) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); AĐ coll.; as *Halictus calceatus* (Scopoli, 1763) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); as *Halictus cylindricus* (Fabricius, 1793) in Petrik (1958); Korlević (1890). [LC]
438. *Lasioglossum clypeare* (Schenck, 1853) in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); as *Halictus clypearis* (Schenck, 1853) in Vorgan (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [NT]
439. *Lasioglossum convexiusculum* (Schenck, 1853) as *Halictus convexiusculum* (Schenck, 1853) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [NT]
440. *Lasioglossum corvinum* (Morawitz, 1877) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus corvinus* Morawitz, 1877 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
441. *Lasioglossum costulatum* (Kriechbaumer, 1873) as *Halictus costulatus* Kriechbaumer, 1873 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897). [NT]
442. *Lasioglossum crassepunctatum* (Blüthgen, 1923) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); as *Halictus crassepunctatus* Blüthgen, 1923 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgan (1955). [DD]
443. *Lasioglossum discum* (Smith, 1853) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); ZM coll.; as *Halictus morbillosus* Kriechbaumer, 1873 in Grozdanić (1971b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgan (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]

444. *Lasioglossum elegans* (Lepelletier, 1841) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus elegans* Lepelletier, 1841 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
445. *Lasioglossum euboense* (Strand, 1909) as *Halictus euboensis* Strand, 1909 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vargin (1955); SG coll. [DD]
446. *Lasioglossum fratellum* (Pérez, 1903) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); AÐ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]
447. *Lasioglossum fulvicorne* (Kirby, 1802) in AÐ coll.; as *Halictus fulvicornis* (Kirby, 1802) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950). [LC]
448. *Lasioglossum glabriusculum* (Morawitz, 1872) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); as *Halictus glabriusculus* Morawitz, 1872 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vargin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
449. *Lasioglossum griseolum* (Morawitz, 1872) as *Halictus griseolus* Morawitz, 1872 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vargin (1955). [LC]
450. *Lasioglossum intermedium* (Schenck, 1868) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
451. *Lasioglossum interruptum* (Panzer, 1798) in Markov (2017); SG coll.; as *Halictus interruptus* (Panzer, 1798) in Grozdanić and Mučalica (1968b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vargin (1955); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
452. *Lasioglossum kussariense* (Blüthgen, 1925) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
453. *Lasioglossum laeve* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus laevis* (Kirby, 1802) in Vargin (1918). [EN]
454. *Lasioglossum laevigatum* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus laevigatus* (Kirby, 1802) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950). [NT]
455. *Lasioglossum laticeps* (Schenck, 1868) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); as *Halictus laticeps* Schenck, 1868 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
456. *Lasioglossum lativentris* (Schenck, 1853) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); ZM coll.; as *Halictus lativentris* Schenck, 1853 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
457. *Lasioglossum leucopus* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus leucopus* (Kirby, 1802) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950). [LC]
458. *Lasioglossum leucozonium* (Schrank, 1781) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); AÐ coll.; ZM coll.; as *Halictus leucozonius* (Schrank, 1781) in Grozdanić (1971b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vargin (1955, 1918); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
459. *Lasioglossum limbellum* (Morawitz, 1876) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus limbellus* Morawitz, 1876 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [DD]
460. *Lasioglossum lineare* (Schenck, 1868) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); SG coll.; as *Halictus linearis* Schenck, 1868 in Grozdanić (1971b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vargin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [DD]

461. **♂***Lasioglossum lissonotum* (Noskiewicz, 1926) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
462. *Lasioglossum lucidulum* (Schenck, 1861) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus lucidulus* (Schenck, 1861) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955). [LC]
463. **♂***Lasioglossum majus* (Nylander, 1852) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); AÐ coll.; as *Halictus major* Nylander, 1852 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Vorgin (1918). [NT]
464. *Lasioglossum mandibulare* (Morawitz, 1866) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus mandibularis* Morawitz, 1866 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955). [NT]
465. **♂***Lasioglossum malachurum* (Kirby, 1802) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); SG coll.; as *Halictus malachurus* (Kirby, 1802) in Grozdanić (1971b, 1969c, 1966, 1960); Grozdanić and Vasić (1970, 1965c); Krunić (1959); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
466. **♂***Lasioglossum marginatum* (Brullé, 1832) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); ZM coll.; as *Halictus marginatus* Brullé, 1832 in Vasić (1979b, 1970, 1966); Grozdanić (1971b, 1970, 1969c, 1966, 1960, 1956); Grozdanić and Vasić (1965c); Krunić (1959); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931); as *Halictus fasciatus* Schenck, 1868 in Vorgin (1955); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
467. **♂***Lasioglossum marginellum* (Schenck, 1853) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
468. *Lasioglossum mesosclerum* (Pérez, 1903) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus mesosclerus* Pérez, 1903 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955). [DD]
469. *Lasioglossum minutissimum* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus minutissimus* (Kirby, 1802) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
470. *Lasioglossum minutulum* (Schenck, 1853) as *Halictus minutulus* (Schenck, 1853) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950). [NT]
471. **♂***Lasioglossum morio* (Fabricius, 1793) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); AÐ coll.; as *Halictus morio* (Fabricius, 1793) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
472. **♂***Lasioglossum nigripes* (Lepeletier, 1841) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); ZM coll.; as *Halictus nigripes* Lepeletier, 1841 in Vasić (1979b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); as *Halictus vulpinus* Nylander, 1853 (nec Fabricius, 1804) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
473. **♂***Lasioglossum nitidiusculum* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); AÐ coll.; as *Halictus nitidiusculus* (Kirby, 1802) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
474. *Lasioglossum nitidulum* (Fabricius, 1804) as *Halictus aeneidorsum* Alfken, 1921 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955). [LC]
475. **♂***Lasioglossum obscuratum* (Morawitz, 1876) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); ZM coll.; as *Halictus obscuratus* Morawitz, 1876 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]

476. *≠Lasioglossum pallens* (Brullé, 1832) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); as *Halictus lineolatus* Lepeletier, 1841 in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
477. *Lasioglossum parvulum* (Schenck, 1853) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus minutus* (Kirby, 1802) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950). [LC]
478. *≠Lasioglossum pauxillum* (Schenck, 1853) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); AĐ coll.; as *Halictus pauxillus* (Schenck, 1853) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
479. *≠Lasioglossum politum* (Schenck, 1853) in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); as *Halictus politus* (Schenck, 1853) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955, 1918); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
480. *▪Lasioglossum pseudocaspicum* (Blüthgen, 1923) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
481. *Lasioglossum punctatissimum* (Schenck, 1853) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus punctatissimus* (Schenck, 1859) in Lebedev (1931). [LC]
482. *≠Lasioglossum puncticolle* (Morawitz, 1872) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); as *Halictus puncticollis* Morawitz, 1872 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
483. *≠Lasioglossum pygmaeum* (Schenck, 1853) in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); ZM coll.; as *Halictus pygmaeus* (Fabricius, 1804) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955). [NT]
484. *Lasioglossum quadrinotatum* (Schenck, 1861) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus quadrinotatus* (Schenck, 1859) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955). [NT]
485. *Lasioglossum quadrinotatum* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus quadrinotatus* (Kirby, 1802) in Vorgin (1955); Apfelbeck (1896). [NT]
486. *▪Lasioglossum rufitarse* (Zetterstedt, 1838) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
487. *Lasioglossum semilucens* (Alfken, 1914) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus semilucens* Alfken, 1914 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
488. *Lasioglossum setulellum* (Strand, 1909) as *Halictus setulellus* Strand, 1909 in Vorgin (1955). [NT]
489. *▪Lasioglossum setulosum* (Strand, 1909) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
490. *≠Lasioglossum sexnotatum* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); AĐ coll.; as *Halictus sexnotatus* (Kirby, 1802) in Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [NT]
491. *≠Lasioglossum sexstrigatum* (Schenck, 1868) in ZM coll.; as *Halictus sexstrigatus* Schenck, 1870[“1869”] in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955). [LC]
492. *Lasioglossum smeathmanellum* (Kirby, 1802) as *Halictus smeathmanellus* K. in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955, 1918); Živojinović (1950); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
493. *Lasioglossum subfasciatum* (Imhoff, 1832) as *Halictus subfasciatus* (Imhoff, 1832) in Lebedev (1931). [EN]
494. *▪Lasioglossum subfulvicorne* (Blüthgen, 1934) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]

495. *Lasioglossum tarsatum* (Schenck, 1868) as *Halictus tarsatus* Schenck, 1868 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955). [NT]
496. *Lasioglossum trichopygum* (Blüthgen, 1923) in ZM coll.; as *Halictus trichopygus* Blüthgen, 1923 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Grozdanić (1966); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a). [DD]
497. *Lasioglossum tricinctum* (Schenck, 1874) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Halictus tricinctus* Schenck, 1874 in Živojinović (1950). [DD]
498. *Lasioglossum truncaticolle* (Morawitz, 1877[“1878”]) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); as *Halictus truncaticollis* Morawitz, 1877[“1878”] in Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
499. *Lasioglossum villosulum* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); SG coll.; as *Halictus villosulus* Kirby, 1802 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
500. *Lasioglossum xanthopus* (Kirby, 1802) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); as *Halictus xanthopus* (Kirby, 1802) in Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955, 1918); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); as *Lasioglossum xanthopum* (Kirby, 1802) in ZM coll. [NT]
501. *Lasioglossum zonulum* (Smith, 1848) as *Halictus zonulus* Smith, 1848 in Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955, 1918); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]

Nomiapis Cockerell, 1919 (3 species)

502. *Nomiapis bispinosa* (Brullé, 1832) as *Nomia ruficornis* Spinola, 1839 in Grozdanić (1971b); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); as *Nomia unidentata* Oliver, 1812 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018). [LC]
503. *Nomiapis diversipes* (Latreille, 1806) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); ZM coll.; as *Nomia diversipes* Latreille, 1806 in Markov (2017); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); AZ coll.; as *Pseudapis diversipes* (Latreille, 1806) in Markov et al. (2016). [LC]
504. *Nomiapis femoralis* (Pallas, 1773) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); ZM coll.; as *Nomia femoralis* (Pallas, 1773) in Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]

Nomioides Schenck, 1867 (1 species)

505. *Nomioides minutissimus* (Rossi, 1790) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); as *Nomioides pulchellus* Schenck, 1859 in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

Rhophitoides Schenck, 1861 (1 species)

506. *≠Rhophitoides canus* (Eversmann, 1852) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); as *Rophites canus* Eversmann, 1852 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); ZM coll. [LC]

Rophites Spinola, 1808 (2 species)

507. *≠Rophites hartmanni* Friese, 1902 in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1918); AZ coll. [DD]
508. *≠Rophites quinquespinosus* Spinola, 1808 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Grozdanić (1971b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Apfelbeck (1896); Mocsáry (1897); ZM coll. [NT]

Seladonia Robertson, 1918 (8 species)

509. *Seladonia confusa* (Smith, 1853) as *Halictus perkinsi* Blüthgen, 1926 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950). [LC]
510. *▪Seladonia gavarnica* (Pérez, 1903) as *Halictus gavarnicus* Pérez, 1903 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
511. *≠Seladonia kessleri* (Bramson, 1879) as *Halictus kessleri* Bramson, 1879 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Vasić (1979b); Grozdanić (1974, 1972b, 1971b, 1966); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); ZM coll. [LC]
512. *≠Seladonia seladonia* (Fabricius, 1794) as *Halictus seladonius* (Fabricius, 1794) in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); as *Halictus geminatus* Pérez, 1903 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950). [LC]
513. *≠Seladonia semitecta* (Morawitz, 1873) as *Halictus semitectus* Morawitz, 1874 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Mocsáry (1897). [EN]
514. *≠Seladonia smaragdula* (Vachal, 1895) as *Halictus smaragdulus* Vachal, 1895 in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); AZ coll. [LC]
515. *≠Seladonia subaurata* (Rossi, 1792) as *Halictus subauratus* (Rossi, 1792) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); AZ coll.; as *Halictus gramineus* Smith, 1849 in Petrik (1958); as *Halictus virescens* Lepeletier, 1841 in Vorgin (1955); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
516. *≠Seladonia tumulorum* (Linnaeus, 1758) as *Halictus tumulorum* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Lebedev (1931); Apfelbeck (1896); AÐ coll.; as *Halictus fasciatus* Nylander, 1848 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931). [LC]

Sphecodes Latreille, 1802 (25 species)

517. *≠Sphecodes albilabris* Fabricius, 1793 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); ZM coll.; as *Sphecodes fuscipennis* (Germar, 1819) in Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
518. *≠Sphecodes alternatus* Smith, 1853 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012). [LC]
519. *Sphecodes crassus* Thomson, 1870 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Sphecodes divisus* Hagens, 1882 in Živojinović (1950); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
520. *Sphecodes cristatus* Hagens, 1882 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). Note: Bogusch and Straka (2012) reported this species as absent on Balkan Peninsula. [NT]
521. *▪Sphecodes croaticus* Meyer, 1922 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
522. *≠Sphecodes ephippius* Linnaeus, 1767 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Vorigin (1918); AĐ coll.; ZM coll.; as *Sphecodes similis* Wesmael, 1836 in Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
523. *Sphecodes ferruginatus* Hagens, 1882 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931); as *Sphecodes rufescens* Hagens, 1874 in Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
524. *Sphecodes geoffrellus* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Sphecodes fasciatus* Hagens, 1882 in Živojinović (1950). [LC]
525. *≠Sphecodes gibbus* Linnaeus, 1758 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Vorigin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
526. *▪Sphecodes hyalinatus* Hagens, 1882 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
527. *≠Sphecodes longulus* Hagens, 1882 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
528. *▪Sphecodes majalis* Pérez, 1903 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
529. *≠Sphecodes miniatus* Hagens, 1882 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); AĐ coll. [LC]
530. *≠Sphecodes monilicornis* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Grozdanić (1971b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); as *Sphecodes subquadratus* Smith, 1845 in Vorigin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
531. *Sphecodes niger* Hagens, 1874 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
532. *≠Sphecodes pellucidus* Smith, 1845 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); AĐ coll. [LC]
533. *▪Sphecodes pseudofasciatus* Blüthgen, 1925 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
534. *Sphecodes puncticeps* Thomson, 1870 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950). [LC]
535. *Sphecodes reticulatus* Thomson, 1870 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

536. *Sphcodes rubicundus* Hagens, 1875 in Lebedev (1931). [NT]
537. *Sphcodes rufiventris* Panzer, 1798 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mocsáry (1897); as *Sphcodes subovalis* Schenck, 1853 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
538. *Sphcodes scabricollis* Wesmael, 1835 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [DD]
539. *Sphcodes schenckii* Hagens, 1882 in Grozdanić (1971b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); ZM coll. [NT]
540. *Sphcodes spinulosus* Hagens, 1875 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
541. *Sphcodes zangherii* Noskiewicz, 1931 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). Note: Bogusch and Straka (2012) stated that the distribution of this species is poorly known due the taxonomical problems in the past, as many specimens of this species (with previously suggested wide distribution in south and central Europe) were missidentified *S. croaticus*. [DD]

Systropha Illiger, 1805 (2 species)

542. *Systropha curvicornis* (Scopoli, 1770) in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Grozdanić (1971b); Grozdanić and Mučalica (1966); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Vorgin (1918), Mocsáry (1897); ZM coll. [NT]
543. *Systropha planidens* Giraud, 1861 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Grozdanić (1971b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1968); Grozdanić and Mučalica (1966); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); SG coll. [VU]

Vestitohalictus Blüthgen, 1961 (2 species)

544. *Vestitohalictus pollinosus* (Sichel, 1860) as *Halictus pollinosus* Sichel, 1860 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); as *Halictus carinaeventris* Fahringer & Friese, 1921 in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
545. *Vestitohalictus vestitus* (Lepelletier, 1841) as *Halictus vestitus* Lepelletier, 1841 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); ZM coll. [LC]

Megachilidae (17 genera; 148 species)

Aglaopis Cameron, 1901 (1 species)

546. *Aglaopis tridentata* (Nylander, 1848) as *Dioxoides tridentata* (Nylander, 1848) in Stanisavljević (2000). [LC]

Anthidiellum Cockerell, 1904 (1 species)

547. *Anthidiellum strigatum* Panzer, 1805 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); as *Anthidium strigatum* (Panzer, 1805) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

Anthidium Fabricius, 1804 (12 species)

548. *Anthidium cingulatum* Latreille, 1809 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
549. ■ *Anthidium diadema* Latreille, 1809 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
550. ≠ *Anthidium florentinum* Fabricius, 1775 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
551. *Anthidium loti* Perris, 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); as *Anthidium variegatum* (Fabricius, 1781) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [DD]
552. ≠ *Anthidium manicatum* Linnaeus, 1758 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Stanisavljević (2000); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
553. ■ *Anthidium montanum* Morawitz, 1864 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
554. ≠ *Anthidium oblongatum* Illiger, 1806 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Krunić et al. (1988); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); AĐ coll.; as *Proanthidium oblongatum* (Illiger, 1806) in Stanisavljević (2000) [LC]
555. ≠ *Anthidium punctatum* Latreille, 1809 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
556. *Anthidium septemspinusum* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Vorgin (1918). [DD]
557. ■ *Anthidium taeniatum* Latreille, 1809 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
558. ■ *Anthidium undulatiforme* Friese, 1917 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
559. ■ *Anthidium undulatum* Dours, 1873 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]

Chelostoma Latreille, 1809 (12 species)

560. ≠ *Chelostoma campanularum* Kirby, 1802 in Stanisavljević (2000); AĐ coll. [LC]
561. *Chelostoma distinctum* Stoeckhert, 1929 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); as *Eriades distinctus* Stoeckhert, 1929 in Živojinović (1950). [LC]

562. ≠ *Chelostoma emarginatum* Nylander, 1856 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); AÐ coll.; also as *Chelostoma appendiculatum* (Morawitz, 1871) in Stanisavljević (2000); as *Eriades emarginatus* Nylander, 1856 and also as *Eriades appendiculatus* in Vorgin (1918). [LC]
563. ≠ *Chelostoma florissomne* Linnaeus, 1758 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); AÐ coll.; SG coll.; as *Chelostoma florissomnis* in Mocsáry (1897); as *Eriades maxillosus* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); as *Eriades florissomnis* Spinola in Vorgin (1918); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
564. ■ *Chelostoma foveolatum* Morawitz, 1868 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
565. ■ *Chelostoma grande* Nylander, 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
566. *Chelostoma handlirschi* Schletterer, 1889 as *Eriades handlirschi* (Schletterer, 1889) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931). Note: According to Müller (2015) there are possible errors in older literature records regarding identification and distribution (“Reliable records exist only for Romania and Bulgaria”) of this species. [DD]
567. ■ *Chelostoma mocsaryi* Schletterer, 1889 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
568. ≠ *Chelostoma nasutum* Pérez, 1895 **New material examined:** 1 ♀; Vlasina Rid; 42.7253°N, 22.3284°E; 22–23 Jul. 2019; A. Đukić leg.; Jelle Devalez det.; AÐ coll. [LC]
569. ≠ *Chelostoma rapunculi* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); AÐ coll.; as *Eriades nigricornis* Nylander, 1848 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
570. ■ *Chelostoma styriacum* Schwarz & Gusenleitner, 1999 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
571. ■ *Chelostoma ventrale* Schletterer, 1889 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]

Coelioxys Latreille, 1809 (17 species)

572. ■ *Coelioxys acanthura* Illiger, 1806 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
573. ≠ *Coelioxys afer* Lepeletier, 1841 as *Coelioxys afra* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); AÐ coll.; SG coll.; as *Coelioxys coronata* Förster, 1853 in Petrik (1958). [LC]
574. *Coelioxys alatus* Förster, 1853 as *Coelioxys alata* Förster, 1853 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Živojinović (1950). [LC]
575. ≠ *Coelioxys argenteus* Lepeletier, 1841 as *Coelioxys argentea* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); ZM coll. [LC]
576. ≠ *Coelioxys aurolimbatus* Förster, 1853 as *Coelioxys aurolimbata* Förster, 1853 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Vorgin (1918); FSUNS. [LC]
577. *Coelioxys brevis* Eversmann, 1852 in Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); as *Coelioxys erythropygata* Förster, 1853 in Petrik (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

578. *Coelioxys conoideus* (Illiger, 1806) as *Coelioxys conoidea* Illiger, 1806 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950). [LC]
579. *Coelioxys echinatus* Förster, 1853 as *Coelioxys echinata* Förster, 1853 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); as *Coelioxys rufocaudata* Smith, 1854 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
580. *Coelioxys elongatus* Lepeletier, 1841 as *Coelioxys elongata* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); ZM coll. [LC]
581. *Coelioxys emarginatus* Förster, 1853 as *Coelioxys emarginata* Förster, 1853 in Stanisavljević (2000); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
582. *Coelioxys haemorrhoea* Förster, 1853 in Stanisavljević (2000); Živojinović (1950). [LC]
583. *Coelioxys inermis* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); as *Coelioxys acuminata* Nylander, 1852 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
584. *Coelioxys mandibularis* Nylander, 1848 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000). [LC]
585. *Coelioxys obtusus* Pérez, 1884 as *Coelioxys obtusa* Pérez, 1884 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); SG coll. [LC]
586. *Coelioxys polycentris* Förster, 1853 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vargin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); SG coll. [LC]
587. *Coelioxys quadridentatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Krunić et al. (1988); ZM coll.; as *Coelioxys quadridentata* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000). [LC]
588. *Coelioxys rufescens* Lepeletier and Audinet-Serville, 1825 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Vargin (1918); Mocsáry (1897); ZM coll. [LC]

Heriades Spinola, 1808 (2 species)

589. *Heriades crenulata* Nylander, 1856 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Heriades crenulatus* Nylander, 1856 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Stanisavljević (2000); Krunić et al. (1988); as *Eriades crenulatus* in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vargin (1955); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
590. *Heriades truncorum* Linnaeus, 1758 in Stanisavljević (2000); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); AÐ coll.; FSUNS; as *Eriades truncorum* (Linnaeus) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

Hofferia Tkalců, 1984 (1 species)

591. *Hofferia schmiedeknehti* Schletterer, 1889 in Stanisavljević (2000). [LC]

Hoplitis Klug, 1807 (17 species)

592. ***Hoplitis acuticornis*** Dufour & Perris, 1840 in Stanisavljević (2000); as *Osmia acuticornis* Dufour & Perris, 1840 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
593. **≠*Hoplitis adunca*** Panzer, 1798 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Stanisavljević (2000); AÐ coll.; as *Hoplites* in Krunić et al. (1988); as *Osmia adunca* (Panzer, 1798) in Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); as *Osmia spinolae* Lapeletier, 1841 in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
594. ***Hoplitis anthocopoides*** Schenck, 1853 in Stanisavljević (2000); as *Osmia caementaria* Gerstäcker, 1869 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
595. ****Hoplitis bisulca*** Gerstäcker, 1869 as *Osmia bisulca* Gerstäcker, 1869 in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
596. **▪*Hoplitis campanularis*** Morawitz, 1877 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
597. **≠*Hoplitis claviventris*** (Thomson, 1872) **New material examined:** 1 ♀; Vlasina Rid; 42.7253°N, 22.3284°E; 21 Jul. 2019; A. Đukić leg.; Andrej Gogala det.; AÐ coll. [LC]
598. **≠*Hoplitis dalmatica*** Morawitz, 1871 in SG coll.; as *Anthocopa dalmatica* (Morawitz, 1871) in Stanisavljević (2000); as *Osmia dalmatica* Morawitz, 1871 in Živojinović (1950). [LC]
599. **▪*Hoplitis illyrica*** Noskiewicz, 1926 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
600. **≠*Hoplitis laevifrons*** Morawitz, 1872 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); ZM coll. [LC]
601. **≠*Hoplitis lepeletieri*** Pérez, 1879 in Stanisavljević (2000); SG coll. [LC]
602. **≠*Hoplitis leucomelana*** Kirby, 1802 in Stanisavljević (2000); AÐ coll.; SG coll.; as *Osmia parvula* Dufour & Perris, 1840 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
603. **≠*Hoplitis loti*** Morawitz, 1867 in Stanisavljević (2000); SG coll. [LC]
604. ***Hoplitis manicata*** Morice, 1901 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); as *Hoplites* in Krunić et al. (1988). [LC]
605. **▪*Hoplitis perezii*** Ferton, 1895 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
606. **▪*Hoplitis praestans*** Morawitz, 1893 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
607. **≠*Hoplitis tridentata*** Dufour & Perris, 1840 in Stanisavljević (2000); SG coll. [LC]
608. **≠*Hoplitis tuberculata*** Nylander, 1848 in Stanisavljević (2000); SG coll. [LC]

Icteranthidium Michener, 1948 (2 species)

609. **▪*Icteranthidium grohmanni*** Spinola, 1838 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
610. ***Icteranthidium laterale*** Latreille, 1809 in Stanisavljević (2000); as *Anthidium laterale* Latreille, 1809 in Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

Lithurgus Latreille, 1825 (2 species)

611. ***Lithurgus chrysurus*** Fonscolombe, 1834 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Krunić et al. (1988); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); Korlević (1890). [LC]

612. *≠Lithurgus cornutus* Fabricius, 1787 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); ZM coll.; also as *Lithurgus cornutus fuscipennis* Lepeletier, 1841 in Stanisavljević (2000); as *Lithurgus cornuta* ssp. *fuscipennis* Lep. in Krunić et al. (1988); as *Lithurgus fuscipennis* Lepeletier, 1841 Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]

Megachile Latreille, 1802 (34 species)

613. *≠Megachile albisecta* Klug, 1817 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); as *Megachile sericans* Fonscolombe, 1832 in Grozdanić (1971b); Vasić (1968); Mocsáry (1897); as *Creightonella albisecta* (Klug, 1817) in Stanisavljević (2000); SG coll. [LC]
614. *▪Megachile albocristata* Smith, 1853 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
615. *▪Megachile alpicola* Alfken, 1924 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
616. *≠Megachile apicalis* Spinola, 1808 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Vorgin (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
617. *Megachile bombycina* Radoszkowski, 1874 in Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
618. *▪Megachile burdigalensis* Benoist, 1940 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
619. *≠Megachile centuncularis* Linnaeus, 1758 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Stanisavljević (2000); Krunić et al. (1988); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); AĐ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]
620. *Megachile circumcincta* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
621. *≠Megachile concinna* Smith, 1879 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Megachile argentata* (Fabricius, 1793) in Stanisavljević (2000); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); ZM Coll. [DD]
622. *≠Megachile deceptor* Pérez 1890 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); FSUNS. [DD]
623. *≠Megachile ericetorum* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Grozdanić (1971b); Grozdanić and Mučalica (1968a); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1918); as *Chalicodoma ericetorum* (Lepeletier, 1841) in Stanisavljević (2000); Krunić et al. (1988); ZM coll. [LC]
624. *Megachile flabellipes* Pérez, 1895 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000). [DD]
625. *Megachile fulvimana* Eversman, 1852 in Stanisavljević (2000). [DD]
626. *≠Megachile genalis* Morawitz, 1880 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); ZM coll. [DD]
627. *▪Megachile giraudi* Gerstäcker, 1869 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]

628. *Megachile hungarica* Mocsáry, 1877 as *Chalicodoma hungarica* Mocsáry, 1877 in Stanisavljević (2000). [DD]
629. *Megachile lagopoda* Linnaeus, 1761 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
630. *Megachile leachella* Curtis, 1828 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); ZM coll. [LC]
631. *Megachile leucomalla* Gerstäcker, 1869 in Stanisavljević (2000); Petrik (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
632. *Megachile ligniseca* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Krunic et al. (1988); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Vorgan (1918). [DD]
633. *Megachile manicata* Giraud, 1861 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
634. *Megachile maritima* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Stanisavljević (2000); Krunic et al. (1988); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
635. *Megachile melanopyga* Costa, 1863 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
636. *Megachile nigriventris* Schenck, 1870 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
637. *Megachile octosignata* Nylander, 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
638. *Megachile parietina* Geoffroy, 1785 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); also as *Chalicodoma muraria* auct. in Apfelbeck (1896); as *Chalicodoma parietina* (Geoffroy, 1785) in Stanisavljević (2000); Krunic et al. (1988). [LC]
639. *Megachile pilicrus* Morawitz, 1877 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); AZ coll. [DD]
640. *Megachile pilidens* Alfken, 1924 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Stanisavljević (2000); Grozdanić (1971b); Lebedev (1931); ZM coll. [LC]
641. *Megachile pyrenaica* Pérez, 1890 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
642. *Megachile pyrenaica* Lepeletier, 1841 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); as *Chalicodoma pyrenaica* (Lepeletier, 1841) in Stanisavljević (2000); ZM coll. [DD]
643. *Megachile rotundata* Fabricius, 1793 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević and Tomanović (2006); Stanisavljević (2000); Krunic et al. (1997, 1995b, 1992b, 1992c, 1985, 1988); Mihajlović et al. (1989); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); ZM coll.; as *Megachile pacifica* (Panzer, 1798) in Vorgan (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
644. *Megachile sculpturalis* Smith, 1853 in Ćetković and Plečaš (2017). **New material examined:** 1 ♂, 1 ♀; Bački Maglić; 45.3686°N, 19.5381°E; 20 Jul. 2019; B. Šikoparija leg.; Sonja Mudri-Stojnić det.; FSUNS.
645. *Megachile versicolor* Smith, 1844 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); AĐ coll. [DD]

646. *≠Megachile willughbiella* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mučalica and Stanisavljević (2005); Stanisavljević (2000); Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); AĐ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]

Osmia Panzer, 1806 (26 species)

647. *≠Osmia andrenoides* Spinola, 1808 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897); Apfelbeck (1896); as *Anthocopa andrenoides* Spinola, 1808 in Stanisavljević (2000); Krunic et al. (1988); SG coll. [LC]
648. *▪Osmia apicata* Smith, 1853 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
649. *≠Osmia aurulenta* Panzer, 1799 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Stanisavljević (2000); Krunic et al. (1988); Grozdanić (1971b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1965c); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Lebedev (1931); SG coll. [LC]
650. *≠Osmia bicolor* Schrank, 1781 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Stanisavljević (2000); Grozdanić (1971b, 1965); Grozdanić and Vasić (1965a, 1965c); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); SG coll. [LC]
651. *≠Osmia bicornis* Linnaeus, 1758 in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a); Vorgin (1955); Grozdanić (1928); AĐ coll.; as *Osmia rufa* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Krunic and Stanisavljević (2006a, 2006b, 2006c, 2006d; 2000; 1996); Krunic et al. (2005, 1999, 1998, 1996, 1995a); Stanisavljević et al. (1999, 1997a, 1997b); Kulinčević et al. (1997); Grozdanić (1971b, 1960); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); ZM coll.; SG coll. [LC]
652. *≠Osmia bidentata* Morawitz, 1876 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Müller (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Grozdanić and Radivojević (1972); Grozdanić (1971b); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); as *Anthocopa bidentata* (Morawitz, 1876) in Stanisavljević (2000); Krunic et al. (1988); as *Osmia affinis* Frivaldszky, 1877 in Petrik (1958); as *Hoplosmia bidentata* (Morawitz, 1876) in SG coll. [LC]
653. *≠Osmia brevicornis* Fabricius, 1798 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Stanisavljević (2000); as *Osmia atrocaerulea* Schilling, 1849 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); as *Osmia panzeri* Morawitz, 1869 in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
654. *≠Osmia caerulescens* Linnaeus, 1758 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Stanisavljević (2000); Krunic et al. (1988); Grozdanić and Vasić (1966a); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); AĐ coll.; SG coll.; as *Osmia aenea* Linnaeus, 1761 in Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
655. *Osmia cephalotes* Morawitz, 1870 as *Osmia cephalotes longiceps* Morawitz, 1876 in Stanisavljević (2000). [LC]

656. *≠Osmia cornuta* Latreille, 1805 in Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Stanisavljević et al. (2013, 2000a, b, 1999, 1997a, b); Stanisavljević (2009, 2000, 1996); Krunić and Stanisavljević (2006a, b, , d); Maccagnani et al. (2007); Krunić et al. (2005, 2001, 1999, 1998, 1996, 1995a, 1992a, 1991, 1989, 1988); Kulinčević et al. (1997); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); AÐ coll.; AZ coll.; ZM coll. [LC]
657. *▪Osmia croatica* Friese, 1893 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
658. *≠Osmia emarginata* Lapeletier, 1841 in Stanisavljević (2000); ZM coll. [LC]
659. *▪Osmia erythrogastra* Fertton, 1905 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
660. *Osmia gallarum* Spinola, 1808 in Stanisavljević (2000); Lebedev (1931). [LC]
661. *▪Osmia jason* Benoist, 1929 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
662. *≠Osmia leaiana* Kirby, 1802 in Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); AÐ coll.; as *Osmia solskyi* Morawitz, 1870 in Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
663. *≠Osmia melanogaster* Spinola, 1808 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Stanisavljević (2000); as *Osmia melanogastra* in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897); as *Osmia aterrima* Morawitz, 1872 in Lebedev (1931). [LC]
664. *≠Osmia niveata* Fabricius, 1804 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); as *Osmia fulviventris* (Panzer, 1798) in Stanisavljević (2000); Krunić et al. (1988); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
665. *▪Osmia padri* Tkalcu, 1974 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]
666. *▪Osmia pilicornis* Smith, 1846 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
667. *≠Osmia rufohirta* Latreille, 1811 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Grozdanić (1971b, 1969b); Grozdanić and Vasić (1965c); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Mocsáry (1897); SG coll; as *Hoplitis rufohirta* (Latreille, 1811) in Stanisavljević (2000); as *Hoplites rufohirta* (Latr.) in Krunić et al. (1988). [LC]
668. *▪Osmia saxicola* Ducke, 1899 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
669. *▪Osmia signata* Erichson, 1835 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
670. *≠Osmia spinulosa* Kirby, 1802 in Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Mudri-Stojnić et al. (2012); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgin (1955); as *Anhocopa spinulosa* (Kirby, 1802) in Stanisavljević (2000). [LC]
671. *Osmia submicans* Morawitz, 1870 in Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
672. *Osmia versicolor* Latreille, 1811 in Stanisavljević (2000); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]

Protosmia Ducke, 1900 (1 species)

673. *Protosmia longiceps* Friese, 1899 as *Eriades longiceps* Friese, 1899 in Vorgin (1918). [DD]

Pseudoanthidium Friese, 1898 (3 species)

674. *Pseudoanthidium scapulare* (Latreille, 1809) as *Paranthidiellum lituratum* (Panzer, 1801) in Stanisavljević (2000); Krunić et al. (1988); as *Anthidium lituratum* (Panzer, 1801) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgan (1918). [DD]
675. **Pseudoanthidium reticulatum* Mocsáry, 1884 as *Anthidium mocsaryi* Friese, 1897 in Mocsáry (1897). [DD]
676. **Pseudoanthidium tenellum* Mocsáry, 1881 as *Anthidium tenellum* Mocsáry, 1881 in Mocsáry (1897). [DD]

Rhodanthidium Isensee, 1927 (2 species)

677. *Rhodanthidium septemdentatum* Latreille, 1809 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); as *Anthidium septemdentatum* Latreille, 1809 in Grozdanić and Vasić (1965c); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
678. ■*Rhodanthidium sticticum* Fabricius, 1787 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [DD]

Stelis Panzer, 1806 (10 species)

679. *Stelis annulata* Lepeletier, 1841 in Stanisavljević (2000); as *Stelis frey-gessneri* Friese, 1885 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [DD]
680. *Stelis breviscula* Nylander, 1848 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Vorgan (1918). [LC]
681. *Stelis minuta* Lepeletier and Audinet-Serville, 1825 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
682. ■*Stelis nasuta* Latreille, 1809 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
683. ■*Stelis odontopyga* Noskiewicz, 1926 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
684. *Stelis ornatula* Klug, 1807 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
685. *Stelis phaeoptera* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931). [DD]
686. *Stelis punctulatissima* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); as *Stelis aterrima* (Panzer, 1798) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897). [LC]
687. ≠*Stelis signata* Latreille, 1809 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); Stanisavljević (2000); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
688. *Stelis simillima* Morawitz, 1876 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Kasperek (2015). [LC]

Trachusa Panzer, 1804 (5 species)

689. ≠*Trachusa byssina* Panzer, 1798 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Stanisavljević (2000); Lebedev (1931); ZM coll. [LC]

690. ■ *Trachusa dumerlei* Warncke, 1980 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [LC]
691. *Trachusa interrupta* Fabricius, 1781 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Kasperek (2017); as *Paraanthidium interruptum* (Fabricius, 1781) in Stanisavljević (2000); as *Anthidium interruptum* (Fabricius, 1781) in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [EN]
692. ■ *Trachusa laticeps* Morawitz, 1873 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [NT]
693. *Trachusa pubescens* Morawitz, 1872 in Kasperek (2017); as *Archianthidium pubescens* Morawitz, 1872 in Stanisavljević (2000); as *Anthidium pubescens* Morawitz, 1872 in Petrik (1958); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Mocsáry (1897). [DD] Note: According to Kasperek (2018), *Trachusa pubescens* sensu lato is a complex of five species, and specimens from Serbia belong to the newly described *Trachusa balcanica* Kasperek, 2018.

Mellitidae (3 genera; 13 species)

Dasyпода Latreille, 1802 (4 species)

694. *Dasyпода argentata* Panzer, 1809 in Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Mocsáry (1897). [NT]
695. ■ *Dasyпода braccata* Eversmann, 1852 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020). [EN]
696. ≠ *Dasyпода hirtipes* (Fabricius, 1793) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Markov (2017); Markov et al. (2016); AĐ coll.; also as *Dasyпода plumipes* Panzer, 1797 in Petrik (1958); as *Dasyпода plumipes* in Grozdanić (1971b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Vorgan (1955, 1918); Živojinović (1950); Lebedev (1931); Mocsáry (1897); ZM coll. [LC]
697. ≠ *Dasyпода pyrotichia* Förster, 1855 **New material examined:** 2 ♀♀; Vlasi-na, Dejanova reka; 42.6888°N, 22.3954°E; 24 Jul. 2019; A. Đukić leg.; Denis Michez det.; AĐ coll. [LC]

Macropis Panzer, 1809 (3 species)

698. ≠ *Macropis europaea* Warncke, 1973 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); AĐ coll.; as *Macropis labiata* (Fabricius, 1804) in Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
699. *Macropis frivaldszkyi* Mocsáry, 1878 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Vorgan (1918); Mocsáry (1897). [NT]
700. *Macropis fulvipes* (Fabricius, 1804) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Lebedev (1931). [LC]

Melitta Kirby, 1802 (6 species)

701. *Melitta budensis* (Mocsary, 1878) in Grozdanić (1971b); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [LC]
702. * *Melitta dimidiata* Morawitz, 1876 in Apfelbeck (1896). [NT]

703. *Melitta haemorrhoidalis* (Fabricius, 1775) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950). [LC]
704. *Melitta leporina* (Panzer, 1799) in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Mudri-Stojnić (2018); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); Morawitz (1876); Apfelbeck (1896). [LC]
705. *Melitta nigricans* Alfken, 1905 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958); Živojinović (1950); AĐ coll.; AZ coll. [LC]
706. *Melitta tricincta* Kirby, 1802 in Kuhlmann et al. (2020); Rafajlović and Seleši (1958). [NT]

Discussion

Of the 706 species from six families of bees presented here for Serbia, more than half (53%) belong to only two families of the group of long-tongued bees, i.e. Apidae (32%) and Megachilidae (21%). Apidae is also the family represented with most genera, 31% of the total number of 58. The genus most rich in species is *Andrena* (fam. Andrenidae) with 104 reported species, followed by *Nomada* (fam. Apidae) – 77 and *Lasioglossum* (fam. Halictidae) – 72 species. Among all genera, 26 (44.8%) are represented with only one or two species. Regarding families, the lowest number of species is recorded within Mellitidae, only 13 (1.8%).

According to the first Red List of European bees (Nieto et al. 2014) and its addition (Rasmont et al. 2017), the pattern found here is similar to that at the European level (Table 1). The first checklist included 1,965 native European bee species, whereas the update presented 2,051 species for Europe and gave the first estimation of 3,408 species for the West Palaearctic biogeographical region. The most prominent and diverse bee family in Europe / West Palaearctic is the Apidae (28.1% / 27.2% of species), while the least diverse is Mellitidae (with only 1.9% / 1.7%). Considering there are approximately 20,000 bee species worldwide, Serbia hosts 3.5% of the total, 20.7% of Western-Palaearctic, and 34.4% of the European bee diversity, according to the list we present in this study. Regarding bee genera, more than half of Western-Palaearctic, and the majority of the European ones are represented in our list, 58 out of 105 and 77, respectively, the latter number updated from 75 (Nieto et al. 2014), since *Halictus* subgenera *Seladonia* and *Vestitohalictus* have recently been erected as distinct genera (Rasmont et al. 2017 and references therein).

For most of the species listed here, newer records (starting with year 2000) have been found in various bibliographic sources and collections. However, for 97 species there are no publicly available records from the 21st century. Furthermore, for 15 of these species the only found data of presence in Serbia are from the 19th century, most of them reported only once, therefore the current presence of these species in the given localities is not certain. Our knowledge of bee fauna is still somewhat fragmentary and uneven among different parts of Serbia, since many localities remain understudied or were investigated a long time ago. A comprehensive future research is needed in order

to confirm and update the data in this provisional list that is meant to represent a review of so far published records and a basis for further studies. Moreover, among 706 species, the presence in Serbia for 314 species was confirmed by determination and review of materials, while data are from literature for 392 species. A third of all the species (227) are included in our list according to only one literature source each, and for almost a quarter (153) of all the species, the only source for their occurrence in Serbia is the “Checklist of the Western Palaearctic Bees” (Kuhlmann et al. 2020). Of the 706 species recorded in total, 510 are also listed in Kuhlmann et al. (2020) as being present in Serbia. Therefore, we present 196 bee species as potential additions to the distribution maps of that checklist. Furthermore, 14 of these species are presented here as the first published records for Serbia.

According to the European Red List (Nieto et al. 2014), most species (more than half) recorded for Serbia and listed here are in the Least Concern category (55.4%), followed by those classified as Data Deficient (31.4%) since there was not enough scientific information to evaluate their risk of extinction. A further 9.1% of species have been assessed as Near Threatened. Therefore, ca. 4% of bee species present in Serbia are considered threatened in Europe; i.e., ten Vulnerable and 18 Endangered species (Table 2). Only one species, *Bombus cullumanus* (fam. Apidae), is listed as Critically endangered at the European level. Three of the species categorised as Endangered according to the European Red List have not been recorded in Serbia in the 21st century. Therefore, Serbia hosts species of conservation concern in Europe; however, the current presence of some species requires re-confirmation and possible re-evaluation of their conservation status. Threatened species mostly belong to families Apidae (13: 6 VU, 6 EN, 1 CR), Colletidae (8: 3 VU, 5 EN) and Halictidae (5: 1 VU, 4 EN); there is one EN species in each of the remaining three families. The pattern is similar to that at the European level, with most threatened species in Apidae, followed by Colletidae and Halictidae. The overall proportion of threatened (VU, EN, and CR) bee species is the same (4%), but the proportional representation of Data Deficient species is higher at 56.7% (Nieto et al. 2014). Among species presented in our list, 77 not included in Kuhlmann et al. (2020) were assessed as Data Deficient (Nieto et al. 2014). Therefore, this study is an addition to the knowledge of the distribution of these species in Europe and thus a contribution to scientific information needed for their threat evaluation. Furthermore, since there is still no national Red List of bees in Serbia, the list presented here provides a baseline for future work in that direction. Only one species of the superfamily Apoidea in Serbia has been listed as protected by national law, *Bombus confusus* (Appendix 2 of the Code on Declaration and Protection of Strictly Protected and Protected Wild Species of Plants, Animals and Fungi, Official Gazette of RS No. 5/2010, 47/2011, 32/2016 and 98/2016); species assessed as Vulnerable in Europe. Comparing global and regional Red Lists has shown that species common within their overall geographical range can be threatened on a local scale, which also highlights the importance to implement conservation measures at various geographical scales (Drossart and Gérard 2020).

Two of the species presented in our list are without the category of threat, since they are not in the European Red List (Nieto et al. 2014) but they have been included in its

addition (Rasmont et al. 2017). One is *Andrena confinis*, previously considered a synonym of *Andrena congruens* but now regarded as a distinct species (Rasmont et al. 2017; Kuhlmann et al. 2020). The second is *Megachile sculpturalis*, native to Eastern Asia. Until recently, European bee fauna has been without allochthonous species; however, this solitary bee has been imported, established, and is expanding rapidly, and the first record for south-east Europe was reported in Serbia in 2017 (Ćetković and Plečaš 2017).

An up-to-date species list is the foundation of biodiversity and conservation work, and knowing which species make up the diverse ecosystems will be critically important in order to protect and restore them. Bees represent one of the key components of global biodiversity, providing vital ecosystem services, being the primary pollinators of most agricultural crops and wild plants. Climate change, land-use change and other anthropogenic pressures have been affecting the diversity of bees throughout the world (Tscharrntke et al. 2005; Winfree et al. 2009; Holzschuh et al. 2010, 2016; Potts et al. 2010; Gill et al. 2012; González-Varo et al. 2013; Senapati et al. 2015). During the last decade, both scientific and public interest in the conservation of pollinators has increased considerably (Drossart and Gérard 2020). Identifying effective conservation practices for bees requires a continuous monitoring to assess their population trends and the most significant threats. The first step towards this aim is the comprehensive knowledge of bee diversity, thus the current study provides a baseline for further research in Serbia. However, our intention is to produce updates, and we hope other researchers will contribute and improve upon this list by providing new information.

Acknowledgements

We gratefully thank Aleksandar Stojanović for providing access to the collections of the Natural History Museum, Belgrade, Serbia and Aleksandra Zatezalo for providing material from collection of the Institute for Nature Conservation of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia. Special thanks to Zsolt Józán (HU), Andrej Gogala (SI), Jelle Devalez (GR), and Denis Michez (BE) for the specimen identifications. We thank Laura Likov for translating literature from Hungarian. We thank Arijana Luburić – Cvijanović for English proofreading. We also thank the editor Thorleif Dörfel, the reviewer Petr Bogusch, and one anonymous reviewer who contributed with constructive suggestions that improved the final version of the paper. The authors acknowledge financial support of the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia (Grant No. 451-03-9/2021-14/200358; 451-03-9/2021-14/200125). The authors declare that no competing interests exist.

References

- Anđelković V (1949) Ekološka ispitivanja na jednom naselju vrste *Halictus quadricinctus* F. Prirodnjak 1.

- Apfelbeck V (1896) Balkanske Apide (pčele). Glasnik zemaljskog muzeja u Bosni i Hercegovini 8: 329–342.
- Bogusch P, Straka J (2012) Review and identification of the cuckoo bees of central Europe (Hymenoptera: Halictidae: *Sphecodes*). Zootaxa 3311(1): 1–41. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3311.1.1>
- Bogusch P, Hadrava J (2018) European bees of the genera *Epeolus* Latreille, 1802 and *Triepeolus* Robertson, 1901 (Hymenoptera: Apidae: Nomadinae: Epeolini): taxonomy, identification key, distribution, and ecology. Zootaxa 4437(1): 1–60. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4437.1.1>
- Burger PR (2010) On the presence of *Colletes hederæ* Schmidt & Westrich and *C. brevisgena* Noskiewicz (Hymenoptera, Colletidae) in Serbia. Osmia 4: 11–14. <https://doi.org/10.47446/OSMIA4.3>
- Ćetković A, Plečaš M (2017) Dalje širenje alohtone azijske pčele u Evropi: prvi nalaz *Megachile sculpturalis* na Balkanu. XI Symposium of entomologists of Serbia, Goč (Serbia), 17–21 September 2017, Book of Abstracts, 82–83.
- Dorchin A, López-Uribe MM, Praz CJ, Griswold T, Danforth BN (2018) Phylogeny, new generic-level classification, and historical biogeography of the *Eucera* complex (Hymenoptera: Apidae). Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution 119: 81–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2017.10.007>
- Drossart M, Gérard M (2020) Beyond the decline of wild bees: Optimizing conservation measures and bringing together the actors. Insects 11(9): e649. [23 pp] <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects11090649>
- Gill RJ, Ramos-Rodriguez O, Raine NE (2012) Combined pesticide exposure severely affects individual- and colony-level traits in bees. Nature 491: 105–108. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11585>
- González-Varo JP, Biesmeijer JC, Bommarco R, Potts SG, Schweiger O, Smith HG, Steffan-Dewenter I, Szentgyörgyi H, Woyciechowski M, Vilà M (2013) Combined effects of global change pressures on animal-mediated pollination. Trends in Ecology & Evolution 28(9): 524–530. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2013.05.008>
- Goulson D, Nicholls E, Botías C, Rotheray EL (2015) Bee declines driven by combined stress from parasites, pesticides, and lack of flowers. Science 347(6229): e1255957. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1255957>
- Grozđanić S (1926) Žuta banatska pčela. Glasnik entomološkog društva 1(1): 1–16.
- Grozđanić S (1928) Zimski sympaedium *Osmia bicorns* L. Glasnik Hrvatskoga prirodoslovnoga društva, Zagreb.
- Grozđanić S (1930) Iz života pčela: primenjena biologija pčelinje zajednice: (*Apis mellifica* L.). Srpska manastirska štamparija, Sremski Karlovci.
- Grozđanić S (1950a) Posmatranje na jednom naselju vrste *Halictus sexcinctus* F. Zbornik radova Instituta za Ekologiju i Biogeografiju, Srpska Akademija Nauka, Beograd 1: 171–174.
- Grozđanić S (1950b) Pčele drvenarice (*Xylocopa violacea* i *Xylocopa valga*) Zbornik radova Instituta za Ekologiju i Biogeografiju, Srpska Akademija Nauka, Beograd 1.
- Grozđanić S (1956) *Halictus marginatus* Brullé kao prelazna forma između solitarnih i socijalnih pčela. Zbornik Matice srpske – serija prirodnih nauka, Novi Sad 9: 73–81.

- Grozđanić S (1958a) Instinkt parenja pčele svilarice (*Colletes cunicularis*). Zbornik Matice Srpske – serija prirodnih nauka, Novi Sad 14: 82–85.
- Grozđanić S (1958b) Pčelinja flora Vojvodine. Matica Srpska, Novi Sad 24: 7–23.
- Grozđanić S (1960) Instinktivna delatnost solitarnih i socijalnih pčela (Apidae). Zbornik Matice Srpske – serija prirodnih nauka, Novi Sad 19: 5–14.
- Grozđanić S (1961) Funkcija mirisnog organa medonosne pčele u raznim situacijama. Zbornik Matice Srpske – serija prirodnih nauka, Novi Sad 20: 24–33.
- Grozđanić S (1965) Zbrinjavanje potomstva kod dvobojne Osmije (*Osmia bicolor*, Hymenoptera). Zbornik Matice srpske – serija prirodnih nauka, Novi Sad 29: 100–106.
- Grozđanić S (1966) Nova posmatranja na nekim vrstama roda *Halictus* (Hymenoptera). Prilog poznavanju filogenetskog postanka pčelinje porodice. Institut za biološka istraživanja – Zbornik radova Beograd 10(15): 2–21.
- Grozđanić S (1968) Biologische Beobachtungen an einige Arten der Gattung *Ceratina* Latr. (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 23: 113–123.
- Grozđanić S (1969a) Neue Untersuchungen an *Eucera excisa* Mocs. (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 24: 57–61.
- Grozđanić S (1969b) Biološka ispitivanja na pčelama (Apoidea) – *Osmia rufohirta* Latr. Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 24: 63–71.
- Grozđanić S (1969c) Zoološka ispitivanja na nekim vrstama *Halictus* (Hymenoptera). Glas SANU, CCLXXVI, Odeljenje Prirodno-matematičkih nauka, Beograd 32: 9–34.
- Grozđanić S (1970) Poseta insekata cvetovima nekih vrsta graorica (*Vicia*, Leguminosae). Zbornik Matice srpske – serija prirodnih nauka, Novi Sad 38: 1–83.
- Grozđanić S (1971a) Biologische Untersuchungen an den Bienen – *Halictus sajoi* (Blüthgen) – (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 26: 151–157.
- Grozđanić S (1971b) Filogenetski postanak pčelinje porodice. Beogradski izdavačko-grafički zavod. Beograd.
- Grozđanić S (1972a) Biološka ispitivanja na pčelama *Halictus maculatus* Sm. i *Halictus asperulus* Pz. (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 27: 71–83.
- Grozđanić S (1972b) Biološka ispitivanja na pčelama (Apoidea, Hymenoptera) – *Halictus kessleri* Bramson. Srpska Akademija Nauka, Beograd 34: 41–54.
- Grozđanić S (1974) Biologische untersuchungen an den bienen (Apoidea, Hymenoptera) – *Halictus kessleri* Bramson. Académie Serbe des Sciences et des Arts, Beograd.
- Grozđanić S, Čolović S (1955a) Nekoliko momenata iz života njivskog bumbara (*Bombus agrorum* F.) u oblasti Fruške gore. Zbornik Matice srpske – serija prirodnih nauka, Novi Sad 9: 107–111.
- Grozđanić S, Čolović SM (1955b) Mlađa (*Corydalis cava*) i njeni posetioci: prilog proučavanjima pčelinje paše u oblasti Fruške gore. Zbornik Matice srpske – serija prirodnih nauka, Novi Sad 8: 69–74.
- Grozđanić S, Stevanović A (1959) Dalja ispitivanja na njivskom bumbaru (*Bombus agrorum*) u oblasti Fruške gore. Zbornik Matice srpske – serija prirodnih nauka, Novi Sad 16: 44–56.

- Grozđanić S, Stevanović A (1965) Posmatranja na kolonijama kosmate pčele *Anthophora parietina* F. Glas SANU, CCLXII, Odeljenje Prirodno-matematičkih nauka, Beograd, 27 pp.
- Grozđanić S, Krunić M (1961) Eksperimentalna biološka ispitivanja na izolovanim maticama u dvomatičnom sistemu pčelarenja. Zbornik Matice Srpske – serija prirodnih nauka, Novi Sad 20: 104–117.
- Grozđanić S, Baranov O (1963) “Disteleologija” bumbara i pčela u svetlosti reflektorne teorije I. P. Pavlova. Prilog proučavanju plastičnosti insekata. Zbornik Matice srpske – serija prirodnih nauka, Novi Sad 24: 21–36.
- Grozđanić S, Vasić Ž (1965a) Prilog poznavanju biologije dvobojne osmije (*Osmia bicolor* Schr., Hymenoptera). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 20: 185–195.
- Grozđanić S, Vasić Ž (1965b) Proučavanje instinktivnog života kosmatih pčela *Anthophora acervorum* L., *A. parietina* F. i *A. crinipes* Sm. (Apoidea, Hym.). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 20: 197–216.
- Grozđanić S, Vasić Ž (1965c) Prilog poznavanju entomofilije u okolini Beograda. Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 20: 217–243.
- Grozđanić S, Vasić Ž (1966a) Nova ispitivanja entomofilije u okolini Beograda. Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 21: 51–70.
- Grozđanić S, Vasić Ž (1966b) Prilog biologiji solitarne pčele *Tetralonia lyncea* Mocs. (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 21: 119–132.
- Grozđanić S, Vasić Ž (1967a) *Tetralonia nana* Morawitz (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 22: 135–143.
- Grozđanić S, Vasić Ž (1967b) *Eucera excisa* Mocsary (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 22: 145–152.
- Grozđanić S, Vasić Ž (1968) Biološka posmatranja na *Systropha planidens* Gir. (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 23: 169–178.
- Grozđanić S, Vasić Ž (1970) Biološka ispitivanja na pčelama – *Halictus malachurus* K. – (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 25: 271–303.
- Grozđanić S, Mučalica Z (1966) Posmatranje na solitarnim pčelama *Systropha planidens* Gir. i *Systropha curvicornis* Scop. (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 21: 133–136.
- Grozđanić S, Mučalica Z (1968a) Über den nestbauinstinkt bei *Megachile ericetorum* Lep. (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Arhiv bioloških nauka 20(1–2): 7–8.
- Grozđanić S, Mučalica Z (1968b) Biologische untersuchungen an den bienen (Apoidea, Hymenoptera) – *Halictus interruptus* Panz. Arhiv bioloških nauka 20(1–2): 9–10.
- Grozđanić S, Mučalica Z (1969) Biologische Untersuchungen an *Anthophora crinipes* Sm. (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 24: 137–141.
- Grozđanić S, Mučalica Z (1973) Prilog poznavanju biologije pčela drvenarica: *Xylocopa violacea* L., *X. valga* Gerst. i *X. cyanesens* Br. (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 28: 103–110.

- Grozđanić S, Radivojević V (1972) Biološka ispitivanja na pčelama – *Osmia bidentata* Mor. i *Anthophora pubescens* F. – (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 27: 63–69.
- Holzschuh A, Steffan-Dewenter I, Tschardt T (2010) How do landscape composition and configuration, organic farming and fallow strips affect the diversity of bees, wasps and their parasitoids? *Journal of Animal Ecology* 79(2): 491–500. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2656.2009.01642.x>
- Holzschuh A, Dainese M, González-Varo PJ, Mudri-Stojnić S, Riedinger V, Rundlöf M, Schep-er J, Wickens JB, Wickens VB, Bommarco R, Kleijn D, Potts SG, Roberts SPM, Smith HG, Vilà M, Vujić A, Steffan-Dewenter I (2016) Mass-flowering crops dilute pollinator abundance in agricultural landscape across Europe. *Ecology Letters* 19(10): 1228–1236. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12657>
- IUCN (2021) The IUCN Red List of threatened species. <https://www.iucnredlist.org/> [Accessed on 31 Mar 2021]
- Kasperek M (2015) The cuckoo bees of the genus *Stelis* Panzer, 1806 in Europe, North Africa and the Middle East: A review and identification guide. *Entomofauna, Supplementum* 18, Maximilian Schwarz, Ansfelden, 144 pp.
- Kasperek M (2017) Resin bees of the anthidiine genus *Trachusa*: Identification, taxonomy, distribution and biology of the Old World species. *Entomofauna, Supplementum* 21, Maximilian Schwarz, Ansfelden (Austria), 151 pp.
- Kasperek M (2018) Taxonomic revision proves *Trachusa pubescens* (Morawitz, 1872) sensu lato to be a complex of allopatric and sympatric species in South-Eastern Europe and Western Asia (Hymenoptera, Apoidea, Anthidiini). *ZooKeys* 764: 111–144. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.764.24581>
- Korlević A (1890) Prilozi fauni hrvatskih opnokrilaca (Hymenoptera). *Glasnik Hrvatskoga naravoslovnoga društva, Zagreb* 5: 189–250.
- Krunić M (1959) Prelazne forme između solitarnih i socijalnih pčela, *Halictus malachurus*, *H. marginatus*, *H. scabiosae*. *Zbornik Matice srpske – serija prirodnih nauka, Novi Sad* 17: 102–110.
- Krunić M (1967) Varijabilitet *Apis mellifica* L. u Jugoslaviji sa posebnim osvrtom na diferencijaciju populacija u Panonskoj niziji. PhD Thesis, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia, 64 pp.
- Krunić M (1986) Medonosne pčele Panonske nizije. Pčesa '86., Bagrem beli 2: 67–71.
- Krunić M (1994) Karakteristike populacija medonosne pčele (*Apis mellifera* L.) u Panonskoj niziji. *Deliblatska peščara. Zbornik radova* 6(1): 223–228.
- Krunić M, Brajković M, Radenović B (1985) Oprašivanje lucerke pomoću solitarne pčele *Megachile rotundata* Fabr. u Jugoslaviji. *Glasilo Društva za semenarstvo Jugoslavije* 2(3): 72–74.
- Krunić MD, Radović IT, Brajković MM (1988) A contribution to the knowledge of the fauna of the Megachilidae family (Hymenoptera) in Yugoslavia (I). *Glas CCCLIII de l'Academie Serbe des Sciences et des Arts, Classe des sciences mathématiques et naturelles, Belgrade* 52: 25–30.
- Krunić M, Janković D, Stanišić T (1989) *Osmia cornuta* Latr. (Megachilidae, Hymenoptera) – Potential orchard pollinator. *Archives of Biological Sciences* 41(1–2): 33–37.

- Krunić MD, Brajković MM, Mihajlović LjS (1991) Management and Utilization of *Osmia cornuta* Latr. for Orchard Pollination in Yugoslavia. Acta Horticulturae 288: 190–193. <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.1991.288.27>
- Krunić M, Brajković M, Tomanović Ž (1992a) Utilization of *Osmia cornuta* Latr. as an orchard pollinator. Archives of Biological Sciences 44(3–4): 19–20.
- Krunić M, Brajković M, Tomanović Ž (1992b) Application of *Megachile rotundata* Fab. for the alfalfa pollination in Yugoslavia. Archives of Biological Sciences 44(3–4): 21–22.
- Krunić M, Brajković M, Mihajlović Lj, Tomanović Ž (1992c) *Megachile rotundata* Fab. (Hymenoptera: Megachilidae) populations and their accompanying fauna in Yugoslavia. In: Proceedings of the Fourth European Congress of Entomology and the XIII Internationale Symposium für die Entomofaunistik Mitteleuropas, Gödöllő (Hungary), 1–6 September 1991, 2: 527–531.
- Krunić M, Terzić L, Brajković M, Nikodinović R (1994) Honeybee (*Apis mellifera* L.) as an Indicator of Environmental Contamination in Parts of Serbia. International symposium and exhibition on environmental contamination in central and eastern Europe, Budapest (Hungary), 20–23 September 1994. Technical University of Budapest / Florida State University, Budapest, 37–38.
- Krunić M, Pinzauti A, Felicioli A, Stanisavljević Lj (1995a) Further observations on *Osmia cornuta* Latr. and *O. rufa* L. as alternative fruit pollinators, domestication and utilization. Archives of Biological Sciences 47(1–2): 59–66.
- Krunić M, Tasei JN, Pinzauti M (1995b) Biology and management of *Megachile rotundata* Fabricius under European conditions. Apicoltura 10: 71–79.
- Krunić M, Stanisavljević Lj, Brajković M, Tomanović Ž (1996) Further investigations of accompanying fauna of orchard bees *Osmia cornuta* Latr. and *O. rufa* L. 7th International congress on the zoogeography and ecology of Greece and adjacent regions, Athens (Greece), 1–5 April 1996, Book of Abstracts, 37.
- Krunić M, Stanisavljević Lj, Brajković M, Tomanović Ž (1997) Uticaj pesticida na gajene populacije lucerkine solitarne pčele *Megachile rotundata* (Fab). u Banatu (Srbija). Zaštita životne sredine gradova i prigradskih naselja. Eko-konferencija 97, Novi Sad (Serbia), 24–26 September 1997, Monografija 1: 319–322.
- Krunić M, Stanisavljević Lj, Brajković M, Tomanović Ž (1998) The effect of cold-hardiness and the way of ending diapause in *Osmia cornuta* and *O. rufa* (Megachilidae, Hymenoptera) on their distribution in Europe. Archives of Biological Science 50(4): 33–34.
- Krunić M, Stanisavljević Lj, Brajković M, Tomanović Ž (1999) Further investigations on the accompanying fauna of orchard bees *Osmia cornuta* Latr. and *O. rufa* (L.). Contributions to the Zoogeography and Ecology of the Eastern Mediterranean Region 1: 287–291.
- Krunić M, Stanisavljević Lj, Brajković M, Tomanović Ž, Radović I (2001) Ecological Studies of *Osmia cornuta* (Latr.) (Hymenoptera, Megachilidae) Populations in Yugoslavia with Special Attention to their Diapause. Proceedings of the eight International Pollination Symposium – Pollination: Integrator of Crops and Native Plant Systems, Mosonmagyaróvár (Hungary), 10–14 July 2000, Acta Horticulturae 561: 297–301. <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2001.561.45>

- Krunić M, Stanisavljević Lj, Pinzauti M, Felicoli (2005) The accompanying fauna of *Osmia cornuta* and *Osmia rufa* and effective measures of protection. Bulletin of Insectology 58(2): 141–152. <http://www.bulletinofinsectology.org/pdfarticles/vol58-2005-141-152krunic.pdf>
- Krunić M, Stanisavljević Lj (2006a) Population management in the mason bee species *Osmia cornuta* (Latr.) and *Osmia rufa* (L.) (Hymenoptera, Megachilidae) for orchard pollination in Serbia. Entomologia generalis 29(1): 27–38. <https://doi.org/10.1127/entomogen/29/2006/27>
- Krunić M, Stanisavljević Lj (2006b) Supercooling points and diapause termination in overwintering adults of orchard bees *Osmia cornuta* and *O. rufa* (Hymenoptera: Megachilidae). Bulletin of Entomological Research 96(3): 323–326. <https://doi.org/10.1079/BER2006423>
- Krunić M, Stanisavljević Lj (2006c) Augmentation of managed populations of *Osmia cornuta* (Latr.) and *O. rufa* (L.) (Hymenoptera: Megachilidae) in South-eastern Europe. European Journal of Entomology 103: 695–697. <https://doi.org/10.14411/eje.2006.091>
- Krunić M, Stanisavljević Lj (2006d) The biology of European orchard bee *Osmia cornuta* (Latr.) (Hymenoptera: Megachilidae). Monograph Paper. Faculty of Biology, University of Belgrade, Belgrade.
- Kuhlmann M, Ascher JS, Dathe HH, Ebmer AW, Hartmann P, Michez D, Müller A, Patiny S, Pauly A, Praz C, Rasmont P, Risch S, Scheuchl E, Schwarz M, Terzo M, Williams PH, Amiet F, Baldock D, Berg Ø, Bogusch P, Calabuig I, Cederberg B, Gogala A, Gusenleitner F, Josan Z, Madsen HB, Nilsson A, Ødegaard F, Ortiz-Sanchez J, Paukkunen J, Pawlikowski T, Quaranta M, Roberts SPM, Sáropataki M, Schwenninger H-R, Smit J, Söderman G, Tomozei B (2020) Checklist of the Western Palaearctic Bees (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Anthophila). <http://westpalbees.myspecies.info> [Accessed on 02 Dec 2020]
- Kulinčević J, Krunić M, Stanisavljević Lj (1997) Medonosne i druge vrste domestifikovanih pčela kao genetički, ekološki i privredni resurs Jugoslavije. Savremena poljoprivreda, Novi Sad 46(1–2): 257–268.
- Lebedev A (1931) Prilog poznavanju jugoslovenskih pčela. Glasnik Jugoslovenskog entomološkog društva, Beograd, Jugoslavija 5–6(1–2): 39–48.
- Maccagnani B, Burgio G, Stanisavljević Lj, Maini S (2007) *Osmia cornuta* management in pear orchards. Bulletin of Insectology 60(1): 77–82. <http://www.bulletinofinsectology.org/pdfarticles/vol60-2007-077-082maccagnani.pdf>
- Markov Z (2017) Fauna insekata polinatora u Vojvodini: diverzitet, brojnost i procena vrednosti ekosistemske usluge polinacije. PhD Thesis, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia, 229 pp.
- Markov Z, Nedeljković Z, Ricarte A, Vujić A, Jovičić S, Józsan Z, Mudri-Stojnić S, Radenković S, Ćetković A (2016) Bee (Hymenoptera: Apoidea) and hoverfly (Diptera: Syrphidae) pollinators in Pannonian habitats of Serbia, with a description of a new *Eumerus* Meigen species (Syrphidae). Zootaxa 4154(1): 27–50. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4154.1.2>
- Michez D, Rasmont P, Terzo M, Vereecken NJ (2019) Bees of Europe. Hymenoptera of Europe 1. NAP Editions, Paris, 547 pp.
- Mihajlović Lj, Krunić MD, Richards KW (1989) Hyperparasitism of *Physocephala vittata* (F.) (Diptera, Conopidae) by *Habrocytus conopidarium* (Bouček) (Hymenoptera, Pteromalidae)

- a pest of *Megachile rotundata* (F.) (Hymenoptera, Megachilidae) in Yugoslavia. Journal of the Kansas Entomological Society 62(3): 418–420. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25085112>
- Mocsáry S (1897) Hymenoptera. A Magyar Birodalom Állatvilága. Fauna Regni Hungariae 1–113.
- Mudri-Stojnić S (2018) Distribucija i dinamika populacija najznačajnijih grupa polinatora u agroekosistemima Vojvodine. PhD Thesis, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia, 196 pp.
- Mudri-Stojnić S, Andrić A, Józán Z, Vujić A (2012) Pollinator diversity (Hymenoptera and Diptera) in semi-natural habitats in Serbia during summer. Archives of Biological Sciences 64(2): 777–786. <https://doi.org/10.2298/ABS1202777S>
- Mučalica Z (1968) Posmatranja na jednoj koloniji *Halictus fulvipes* Klug. (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Glasnik Prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 23: 179–183.
- Mučalica Z (1984) Nove vrste Apoidea nađene u Jugoslaviji. Entomološki kolokvij kratki sadržaj referata, Jugoslovensko entomološko društvo, Zemun-Beograd.
- Mučalica Z (1987a) Rasprostranjenje i životni ciklus vrste *Anthophora parietina* F. (Anthophorinae, Apoidea). Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 42: 85–102.
- Mučalica Z (1987b) Temperature smrzavanja razvojnih stupnjeva i adulta *Anthophora parietina* F. i *Anthophora crinipes* Sm. (Hymenoptera) i njihovih parazita. Ekologija Beograd 22(2): 77–82.
- Mučalica Z (1990) Prilog poznavanju biologije *Anthophora crinipes* Sm. (Hymenoptera, Apoidea). Zbornik Matice Srpske – serija prirodnih nauka, Novi Sad 79: 41–55.
- Mučalica Z (1997) Natural enemies of solitary bee populations of *Anthophora* with a special reference to *Anthophora crinipes* Sm. and *A. parietina* F. (Hymenoptera: Anthophoridae). Acta entomologica serbica 2 (1/2): 47–59.
- Mučalica Z, Stanisavljević Lj (2005) Prilog poznavanju biologije gnežđenja solitarne pčele *Megachile willughbiella* (Kirby, 1802) (Hymenoptera: Apoidea: Megachilidae). In: Simpozijum entomologa Srbije, Bajina Bašta (Serbia), 25–29 September 2005, Zbornik plenarnih referata i rezimea, 35.
- Müller A (2015) Palearctic *Chelostoma* bees of the subgenus *Gyrodromella* (Megachilidae, Osmiini): biology, taxonomy and key to species. Zootaxa 3936(3): 408–420. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3936.3.6>
- Müller A (2018) Palearctic *Osmia* bees of the subgenus *Hoplosmia* (Megachilidae, Osmiini): biology, taxonomy and key to species. Zootaxa 4415(2): 297–329. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4415.2.4>
- NBN (2020) NBN (The National Biodiversity Network) Atlas. <https://nbnatlas.org/> [Accessed on 13 Dec 2020]
- Nieto A, Roberts SPM, Kemp J, Rasmont P, Kuhlmann M, García Criado M, Biesmeijer JC, Bogusch P, Dathe HH, De la Rúa P, De Meulemeester T, Dehon M, Dewulf A, Ortiz-Sánchez FJ, Lhomme P, Pauly A, Potts SG, Praz C, Quaranta M, Radchenko VG, Scheuchl E, Smit J, Straka J, Terzo M, Tomozii B, Window J, Michez D (2014) European Red List of bees. Publication Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- Notton DG, Dathe HH (2008) William Kirby's types of *Hylaenus* Fabricius (Hymenoptera, Colletidae) in the collection of the Natural History Museum, London. Journal of Natural History 42(27): 1861–1865. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222930802128512>

- Official Gazette of RS No. 5/2010, 47/2011, 32/2016 and 98/2016 (2021) Code on Declaration and Protection of Strictly Protected and Protected Wild Species of Plants, Animals and Fungi. <https://www.pravno-informacioni-sistem.rs/SlGlasnikPortal/eli/rep/sgrs/ministarstva/pravilnik/2010/5/3/reg> [Accessed on 31 Mar 2021]
- Official Gazette of RS No. 48/19 (2021) Spatial Plan Republic of Serbia 2021–2035. <http://media1.opstinamalocrnice.rs/2020/03/PROSTORNI-PLAN-REPUBLIKE-SRBIJE-OD-2021.-DO-2035.GODINE.pdf> [Accessed on 31 Mar 2021]
- Petrik A (1958) Entomofauna Deliblatske peščare. Rad Vojvodanskih muzeja, Novi Sad 7: 87–113.
- Potts SG, Biesmeijer JC, Kremen C, Neumann P, Schweiger O, Kunin WE (2010) Global pollinator declines: trends, impacts and drivers. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 25(6): 345–353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2010.01.007>
- Rafajlović A, Seleši Đ (1958) Iz entomološke zbirke prof. A. Tauberta (Subotica). Zbornik Matice Srpske – serija prirodnih nauka, Novi Sad 14: 86–142.
- Rasmont P, Haubruge E [Eds] (2020) Atlas Hymenoptera. <http://www.atlashymenoptera.net> [Accessed on 13 Dec 2020]
- Rasmont P, Franzén M, Lecocq T, Harpke A, Roberts SPM, Biesmeijer JC, Castro L, Cederberg B, Dvorač L, Fitzpatrick Ú, Gonseth Y, Haubruge E, Mahé G, Manino A, Michez D, Neumayer J, Ødegaard F, Paukkunen J, Pawlikowski T, Potts SG, Reemer M, Settele J, Straka J, Schweiger O (2015) Climatic Risk and Distribution Atlas of European Bumblebees. *Biorisk* 10 (Special Issue), Pensoft Publishers, Sofia, 246 pp.
- Rasmont P, Devalez J, Pauly A, Michez D, Radchenko VG (2017) Addition to the checklist of IUCN European wild bees (Hymenoptera: Apoidea). *Annales de la Société entomologique de France (N.S.)* 53(1): 17–32. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00379271.2017.1307696>
- Schwarz M, Gusenleitner F, Mazzucco K (1999) Weitere Angaben zur Bienenfauna Österreichs. Vorstudie zu einer Gesamtbearbeitung der Bienen Österreichs III (Hymenoptera, Apidae). *Entomofauna* 20(31): 461–524.
- Schwenninger HR (2015) Revision of the Western Palearctic species of the *Andrena taraxaci*-group with description of four new species (Hymenoptera: Andrenidae). *Stuttgarter Beiträge zur Naturkunde A, Neue Serie* 8: 251–270.
- Senapathi D, Carvalheiro LG, Biesmeijer JC, Dodson C-A, Evans RL, McKerchar M, Morton RD, Moss ED, Roberts SPM, Kunin WE, Potts SG (2015) The impact of over 80 years of land cover changes on bee and wasp pollinator communities in England. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 282(1806): e20150294. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2015.0294>
- Smit J (2018) Identification key to the European species of the bee genus *Nomada* Scopoli, 1770 (Hymenoptera: Apidae), including 23 new species. *Entomofauna, Monographie* 3, Maximilian Schwarz, Ansfelden, 253 pp.
- Stanisavljević Lj (1996) Uticaj prateće faune na populacije novodomesifikovanih solitarnih pčela *Osmia cornuta* Latr. i *O. rufa* L. (Megachilidae, Hymenoptera). Magister's thesis, University of Belgrade, Belgrade.
- Stanisavljević Lj (2000) Idioekološka studija vrsta *Osmia cornuta* (Latr.) i *O. rufa* (L.) (Megachilidae, Hymenoptera) sa posebnim osvrtom na njihov status i značaj kao opravišača biljaka. PhD Thesis, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, 304 pp.

- Stanisavljević Lj (2009) Doprinos poznavanju umnožavanja gajenih populacija evropske pčele voćnjaka *Osmia cornuta* u Srbiji. In: XVII Naučno savetovanje sa međunarodnim učesćem “Kvalitet meda i selekcija medonosne pčele”, Poljoprivredni fakultet, Zemun (Serbia), 7 February 2009, 41–50.
- Stanisavljević Lj (2013) Megachilidae (Apoidea: Hymenoptera) of Mt. Fruška Gora. In: Šimić S (Ed.) Invertebrates (Invertebrata) of the Fruška Gora Mountain. III. Matica Srpska, Novi Sad, 165–179.
- Stanisavljević Lj, Tomanović Ž (2006) Proizvodnja semena lucerke pomoću solitarne pčele *Megachile rotundata* (Fab.) (Hymenoptera: Megachilidae) U Srbiji. Zbornik abstrakata Trećeg simpozijuma sekcije za oplemenjivanje organizama društva genetičara Srbije i četvrtog naučno-stručnog simpozijuma iz selekcije i semenarstva društva selekcionara i semenara Srbije, Zlatibor (Serbia), 16–20 May 2006, 167.
- Stanisavljević Lj, Nedić N (2008) Uloga pčela (Hymenoptera: Apoidea) u oprašivanju voćaka. In: XXIII Savetovanje – Unapređenje proizvodnje voća i grožđa, Grocka (Serbia), 25 July 2008. Institut PKB Agroekonomik, Beograd, Zbornik naučnih radova 14(5): 89–96.
- Stanisavljević Lj, Krunic M, Brajković M, Tomanović Ž (1997a) Synchronization of emergence of *Osmia cornuta* Latr. and *O. rufa* L. (Hymenoptera, Megachilidae) with their cleptoparasites *Chaetodactylus osmiaae* (Acarina, Chaetodactylidae) and *Cacoxenus indagator* Loew (Diptera, Drosophilidae). In: Biodiversity and ecological problems of Balkan fauna, Sofia, 26–29 May 1997, Abstracts, 84.
- Stanisavljević Lj, Krunic M, Brajković M, Tomanović Ž (1997b) Utvrđivanje optimalnog trajanja hibernacije kod solitarnih pčela *Osmia cornuta* Latr. i *O. rufa* L. (Hymenoptera, Megachilidae) u eksperimentalnim uslovima. In: Simpozijum entomologa Srbije, Goč, 2–4 October 1997, Zbornik rezimea, 53.
- Stanisavljević Lj, Krunic M, Brajković M, Tomanović Ž (1999) Prateća fauna kod gajenih populacija solitarnih pčela *Osmia cornuta* Latr. i *O. rufa* L. (Hymenoptera, Megachilidae) u Srbiji. In: Simpozijum entomologa Srbije, Goč, 21–23 October 1999, Zbornik rezimea, 40.
- Stanisavljević Lj, Krunic M, Brajković M, Tomanović Ž, Radović I (2000a) Ecological studies of *Osmia cornuta* (Latr.) (Hymenoptera, Megachilidae) populations in Yugoslavia with special attention to their diapause. The 8th International Pollination Symposium, Mosonmagyaróvár, 10–14 July 2000, Book of Abstracts, 43.
- Stanisavljević Lj, Krunic M, Brajković M, Tomanović Ž, Radović I (2000b) The study of accompanying fauna of *Osmia cornuta* (Latr.) (Hymenoptera, Megachilidae) populations in Yugoslavia. In: The 8th International Pollination Symposium, Mosonmagyaróvár, 10–14 July 2000, Book of Abstracts, 44.
- Stanisavljević Lj, Popović A, Četković A (2013) Razlike u morfologiji krila kod obojenih formi vrste *Osmia cornuta* (Hymenoptera: Megachilidae) pomoću geometrijske morfometrije. In: Simpozijum entomologa Srbije, Tara, 18–22 September, Zbornik rezimea, 64.
- Stevanović A, Lazarov A (1977) Prilog poznavanju gnežđenja *Bombus muscorum* L. (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). Glasnik prirodjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke 32: 105–112.
- Stevanović V, Stevanović B (1995) Osnovni klimatski, geološki i pedološki činioci biodiverziteta kopnenih ekosistema Jugoslavije. In: Stevanović V, Vasić V (Eds) Biodiverzitet Jugo-

- slavije sa pregledom vrsta od međunarodnog značaja. *Ecolobri*, Biološki fakultet, Beograd, 75–115.
- Tschamtker T, Klein AM, Kruess A, Steffan-Dewenter I, Thies C (2005) Landscape perspectives on agricultural intensification and biodiversity – ecosystem service management. *Ecology letters* 8(8): 857–874. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2005.00782.x>
- Vasić Ž (1966) Nekoliko momenata iz života vrste *Halictus marginatus* Brullé (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). *Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke* 21: 103–118.
- Vasić Ž (1967) *Halictus quadricinctus* F. et le probleme de la polygynie. *Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke* 21: 181–187.
- Vasić Ž (1968) Aktivnost vrste *Megachile sericans* Fonsc. na izgradnji gnezda (Apoidea, Hymenoptera). *Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke* 23: 201–210.
- Vasić Ž (1970) Ritam dnevnog saobraćaja sa okolinom pomoćnih ženki *Halictus marginatus* Brullé (Hymenoptera, Halictidae). *Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke* 25: 337–348.
- Vasić Ž (1979a) Poliginija kod *Halictus scabiosae* Rossi (Hymenoptera, Apoidea). *Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke* 34: 211–217.
- Vasić Ž (1979b) Die Überwinterung einiger Arten der Gattung *Halictus* (Hymenoptera, Apoidea). *Glasnik prirodnjačkog muzeja u Beogradu, serija B, biološke nauke* 34: 219–221.
- Vlatković B (1957) Pčele sjeničke kotline i visoravni Peštera i uslovi pčelarenja. *Acta Veterinaria* 7(2): 3–18.
- Vorgin V (1918) Pregled Apidae hrvatske Slavonije i hrvatskog Primorja s obzirom na faunu Apida Dalmacije. *Glasnik Hrvatskoga prirodoslovnoga društva, Zagreb* 30: 1–4.
- Vorgin V (1955) Prilog fauni Hymenoptera-Aculeata iz Jugoslavije. *Zaštita bilja, Beograd* 31 (Supplement): 1–72.
- Winfree R, Aguilar R, Vázquez DP, LeBuhn G, Aizen MA (2009) A meta-analysis of bees' responses to anthropogenic disturbance. *Ecology* 90(8): 2068–2076. <https://doi.org/10.1890/08-1245.1>
- Zicha O [Ed.] (2020) BioLib (Biological Library). <https://www.biolib.cz> [Accessed on 13.12.2020]
- Živojinović S (1950) Fauna insekata šumske Domene Majdampek (Entomološka monografija). Srpska Akademija Nauka, Posebna izdanja knjiga CLX Institut za Ekologiju i Biogeografiju, Beograd, 252 pp.